

JUPITER'S RING SYSTEM RESOLVED: PHYSICAL PROPERTIES
INFERRED FROM THE VOYAGER IMAGES

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The 25 Voyager images represent nearly all of the data now in existence on Jupiter's insubstantial ring system. We have developed techniques which allow a surprising amount of information to be extracted from these data. Our analysis involves precise determination of the geometry and smear in each image, and uses pixel averaging methods which permit vast improvement in signal over noise. In addition, contrast enhancement via computer graphics has made it possible to see many subtle features in the frames which had been previously overlooked.

The Jovian ring system consists of three components: the bright ring, vertically-extended halo and external "gossamer" ring. The interior disk reported by previous investigators is absent.

The bright ring has an abrupt (< 200 km wide) outer boundary centered at orbital radius 129130 ± 100 km, and a broader inner boundary at ~ 122000 km. It reveals fine structure on scales of a few hundred km, some of which is associated with the embedded satellites Adrastea and Metis. It contains a large population of micron-sized grains, which obey a power-law size distribution $n(r) \propto r^{-p}$, with $p = 2.5 \pm 0.5$. Here $n(r)dr$ is the number of particles per unit ring area with radii between r and $r+dr$. These

grains account for an optical depth $\tau = 1-6 \times 10^{-6}$ for $r < 100 \mu\text{m}$. The ring also contains a separate population of larger bodies, which are rough, dark and red, and have an optical depth $\sim 3 \times 10^{-6}$; these act as sources for the tinier grains.

The halo is a crudely toroidal cloud of material, running from the ring's inner boundary roughly halfway down to the Jovian cloudtops. It is symmetric about the ring plane, and extends for $\sim 10^4$ km above and below it. Its particle size distribution is not markedly different from the micron-sized population in the bright ring.

In addition, we have discovered a much fainter ring, which extends outward from the main ring to an orbit of $\sim 210,000$ km, though with ever-decreasing brightness. Its mean intensity is $\sim 5\%$ that of the main ring, and its only notable feature is a $\sim 20\%$ brightness enhancement at synchronous orbit.

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Mark Showalter was born on December 5, 1957. Appearing on the scene two months too late to see Sputnik I, he can truthfully claim to be a child of the Space Age.

Until age 17, he lived with his family in suburban Bucks County, Pennsylvania, outside Philadelphia. Mark displayed scientific curiosity at a young age although, as his mother will attest, his earliest "experiments" had unfavorable consequences for the living room furniture. In 1975 he graduated from Council Rock High School and left home for Oberlin College, somewhere in rural Ohio. There he majored in physics and mathematics. Despite his unsuccessful attempt at building a radio telescope for his senior honors project, he was awarded his B.A. in 1979, with highest honors in physics.

During the spring of 1979, as he was trying to decide the future course for his life, Voyager I flew past Jupiter and made his decision much easier. That event more than any other solidified his resolve, as a senior physics major with a vague interest in astronomy, to pursue a career in planetary science. At the time, however, the strange picture with a lot of jagged lines, which Walter Cronkite reported as the discovery of a Jovian ring system, made no extraordinary impression on him.

He moved straight on from college to graduate school at Cornell University. Cornell was chosen in part for its academic credentials, and in part because rural Ithaca is much like the childhood home he thinks he remembers. Here he discovered the joys of running, swimming, skiing, sailing, photography, travel, and coffeehouse management. In the meantime, he managed to complete this thesis. For the moment he plans to remain at Cornell, as a research associate in the Astronomy Department. Thus he will continue much as he has in the past, except that now, for the first time since age four, he will not be a student.

DEDICATION

My father used to joke that, regardless of whether heredity or environment played the greater role in my development, he could still take some credit for my achievements. With love and gratitude, I dedicate this thesis to his memory.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I have had the privilege of working with numerous scientists during my tenure as a graduate student at Cornell, and they have all contributed to my development as a researcher. I regard it as a challenge to live up to the high standards they have set.

The foremost of these is Professor Joe Burns, who has played the role of thesis advisor with skill, dedication, patience and a welcome sense of humor. I thank him for offering his frequent hospitality and for seeking to broaden my horizons, as well as for teaching me some orbital mechanics. My thesis was further strengthened by his renowned skills as an editor.

Both Joe and Dr. Jeff Cuzzi of NASA/Ames encouraged me to take a new look at the Jovian ring images, despite my thinly-veiled lack of enthusiasm. Jeff guided me through the earliest stages of this research, during a productive and worthwhile, if rainy, stay in California. He introduced me to the joys of color computer graphics and image processing and, in the meantime, taught me a little photometry.

My other academic committee members at Cornell, Jim Houck, Steve Ostro and Saul Teukolsky, as well as my "extra member," Phil Nicholson, contributed to all aspects of my education and research. Their criticisms strengthened this thesis considerably. Numerous

other scientists have provided helpful advice at various stages in my research, including Bonnie Buratti, Andy Collins, Ralph Kahn, Jim Pollack, Damon Simonelli, Steve Synnott, Peter Thomas, Reid Thompson and Joe Veverka. I am particularly indebted to Glenn Garneau and Candy Hansen for their help, patience and forbearance during a week of emergency image processing at JPL.

This research required the writing and debugging of a mass of RATFOR code somewhat longer than the thesis itself; it would not have been possible without the continued help and advice of Robin Gowin. Ken Bilski and Paul Swan of NASA/Ames created the earliest versions of some of the software, and I thank them for letting me pirate it. My computing at Ames was also greatly assisted by Dave Anderson and Marion Legg.

Margaret Dermott may be credited with making SPIF a pleasant and productive place to do research. Barbara Boettcher drafted the superb line drawings of this thesis. Fred Jaquin and Steve Lee guided me through the preparations of the photographic figures. I am especially grateful to Mary Roth for her speedy and reliable word processing, including spelling and punctuation corrections, with a smile; this thesis could never have seen the light of day without her expert midwifery.

In addition to those cited above for their direct input into my graduate work, I have been blessed by a number of good friends who have made my years at Cornell especially enjoyable. All of my fellow grad students in astronomy have made the Space Sciences

Building a more pleasant place to work, even between the hours of midnight and 6 am. I thank them for reminding me that there are lots of interesting things in this universe besides dust around Jupiter. I also thank two inanimate objects, the Unmuzzled Ox (a coffeehouse) and the Escargot (a sailboat), but mainly the "regulars" thereof, for providing many hours of amiable distractions.

Looking back, I don't think anyone played a greater role in cultivating my scientific curiosity than my grandfather, Robert Gilfillan. I thank him for helping me grow a pineapple plant, for teaching me how to use a slide rule, and for giving me a glass prism on my eleventh birthday. I think he would have been happy to see where it all led.

All the members of my "extended" family, and particularly my mother, Jay and Amy, have stood beside me throughout this endeavor. As much as it means to finish my thesis, it means more to be able to share it with them, and to thank them for the love and support which made it possible.

Finally, for the Jovian ring system's minimalist splendor, and for my own humble skills at describing it, I offer thanks to our shared creator.

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CHAPTER 1

THE JOVIAN RING SYSTEM

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Upon its discovery, the Jovian ring system's diaphanous character made it unique within the known family of planetary rings. Aside from Saturn's mysterious E ring, all other rings had revealed distinct structure and were thought to carry a substantial complement of macroscopic bodies. We now recognize that this was simply a selection effect, for faint rings are, by definition, harder to detect. The G and E rings of Saturn are also quite tenuous (i.e., optical depth $\tau \ll 1$; cf. Cuzzi et al., 1984 and references therein; Burns et al., 1984 and references therein), as is a recently-discovered extension to Ring A (Graps et al., 1984; Burns et al., 1983). We await Voyager's passage through the orbital systems of Uranus and Neptune to see what new diffuse structures, if any, might be revealed.

Such rings are of particular interest because the physical processes acting are somewhat different from those in the more substantial ring systems. For the tiny particles which apparently compose these rings, interparticle collisions are infrequent and so must play a lesser role, whereas electromagnetic and drag forces play a greater one. In addition, the tiny grains must have quite

limited lifetimes in such energetic plasma environments.

After an initial flurry of interest following its discovery, Jupiter's ring system suffered neglect under an influx of newer, higher-quality data about the rings of Saturn and Uranus. Analysis of the Voyager Jovian ring images (Smith et al., 1979a,b; Owen et al., 1979; Jewitt and Danielson, 1981; Tyler et al., 1981; Jewitt, 1982) ceased once there arose a general consensus that very little additional information could be gleaned from this limited catalog of faint, fuzzy, smeared images. Theoretical studies of the ring system have continued (Burns et al., 1980, 1984; Consolmagno, 1980, 1983; Grün et al., 1980; Johnson et al., 1980; Morfill et al., 1980a-d; Schaffer and Burns, 1984) but they have been frustrated by the fact that the available observations seem insufficient to distinguish between competing models.

We undertook a new examination of the Voyager images in the hopes that some further trace of information from them might prove diagnostic. Using new software for the processing and interpretation of (specifically) planetary ring images, we have been surprised by the wealth of information that these seemingly-unexceptional frames contain. Contrast enhancement, using color computer graphics, has enabled us to see subtle features in the images which had been previously overlooked. Careful modelling of the geometry and smear in each frame, combined with techniques for averaging image intensity values as a function of arbitrary geometric coordinates, has made it possible to measure intensities and

their variations at levels which were not previously attainable. Thus, the work presented herein significantly refines and advances the investigations of our predecessors.

1.2 THE VOYAGER IMAGES

Jupiter's ring system was discovered on March 4, 1979, as Voyager 1 passed through the planet's equatorial plane, in an image (FDS* 16368.19; Fig. 1.1) specifically intended to search for a faint ring system. The narrow angle (NA) camera captured the ring's outer terminus, against the backdrop of open star cluster NGC 2632. Though badly smeared and difficult to interpret quantitatively, this image showed the unmistakable presence of ring material. Wobble in the camera's pointing during this very lengthy (672 s) exposure introduced thirteen separate kinks into the numerous star trails visible, and produced seven independent edge-on views of the ring. A wide angle (WA) exposure taken at the same time (FDS 16368.20) was saturated by the large flux of high-energy particles surrounding Jupiter, and failed to show the ring (Smith et al., 1979a).

Voyager 2 was then programmed to take a sequence of two dozen ring images, summarized by Owen et al. (1979). They have exposure times of 15 and 96 s, substantially briefer than the discovery

*For cataloging purposes, each image is labelled by Voyager's Flight Data System (FDS) count at the time of the exposure's end. The integer piece counts the number of 48-minute intervals which have elapsed since the spacecraft was launched, while the fractional piece counts sixty 48-second subintervals, from .00 to .59.

FIGURE 1.1. The Jovian ring discovery image, FDS 16368.19, taken as Voyager 1 passed through the equatorial plane. The smeared edge-on ring is visible as a broad stripe from upper left toward lower right. The numerous jagged lines are star trails.

image. Nevertheless, these times are much longer than is typical for exposures of the planet and its satellites (generally < 3 s), so the frames still show significant smear, which complicates their interpretation. Half of the images were taken in backscattered light (i.e., small solar phase angles) as Voyager approached the planet, much like the discovery frame. In these views the almost fully-lit Jovian disk was just outside the visible field; this bright source partly contaminated the images, so that the ring is only visible as a tiny brightness increment atop a sea of scattered light. The other half were taken in forward-scattered light, during the brief period as the spacecraft passed through Jupiter's shadow. Here the planetary light contamination was eliminated and the ring was found to be especially bright (Owen et al., 1979), so substantially better images were obtained. Figure 1.2 displays the geometry of the Voyager 2 encounter. For quick reference in later parts of this thesis, Table 1.1 summarizes the complete Voyager Jovian ring library, including each frame's geometry and content.

During the Voyager 2 approach, a pair of NA frames taken from roughly 2° above the ring plane (FDS 20612.27, .31; Fig 1.3), first revealed the ring's inner boundary. The ring is clearly rather narrow and very faint, but little more can be established. Fourteen hours later a mosaic of nine NA images was taken from very close to the ring plane (FDS 20630.20-.52; Fig. 1.4) plus a single WA image of the same field (FDS 20630.53; Fig. 1.5). The NA mosaic includes a set of three images through color filters (FDS 20630.36,

FIGURE 1.2. The Voyager 2 trajectory through the Jovian system, including the geometry for the ring images. Based on Owen et al.'s Fig. 1 (1979).

TABLE 1.1. Jovian Ring Image Summary

FDS	Camera/filter	T _{exp} (s)	Elev (°)	Range (10 ³ km)	Phase (°)	Content ^a
16368.19 (V1)	NA clear	672	0.01	1215	0.53-0.57	BR
20612.27 (V2)	NA clear	96	2.40	2003	2.5-2.7	BR
20612.31	NA clear	96	2.39	2001	2.6-2.7	BR
20630.20	NA clear	96	-0.02	1407	16.4-16.8	nothing
20630.24	NA clear	96	-0.04	1405	16.8-17.2	BR
20630.28	NA clear	96	-0.05	1403	17.2-17.6	BR
20630.32	NA clear	96	-0.06	1402	17.7-18.1	BR
20630.36	NA violet	96	-0.07	1400	17.8-18.3	BR
20630.40	NA orange	96	-0.08	1398	17.8-18.3	BR
20630.44	NA green	96	-0.09	1396	18.0-18.4	BR
20630.48	NA clear	96	-0.10	1394	18.4-18.8	BR,Adrastea
20630.52	NA clear	96	-0.12	1392	18.9-19.0	BR terminus
20630.53	WA clear	15.36	-0.12	1391	18.0-19.0	BR terminus, H?,Adrastea
20691.27	WA violet	96	-2.08	1500	175.4-176.2	BR, H, shadow
20691.31	WA orange	96	-2.07	1503	175.4-176.3	BR, H, shadow
20691.35	WA orange	96	-2.06	1505	176.2-176.9	BR, H, shadow
20691.39	WA violet	96	-2.05	1507	176.2-176.8	BR, H, shadow
20692.37	NA clear	96	-1.89	1539	175.5-175.8	BR, H
20692.41	NA clear	96	-1.88	1541	175.3-175.6	BR, H
20692.45	NA clear	96	-1.87	1544	174.9-175.2	BR, H
20692.49	NA clear	96	-1.86	1546	174.5-174.9	BR, H
20692.53	NA clear	96	-1.85	1548	174.2-174.6	BR, H
20692.57	NA clear	96	-1.84	1550	174.0-174.2	BR, H
20693.01	NA clear	96	-1.83	1552	173.8	ER
20693.02	WA clear	15.36	-1.82	1553	173.8-174.7	BR ansa, H, ER

^aContent abbreviations: BR = bright ring; H = halo; ER = external ring.

FIGURE 1.3. Voyager 2 inbound views of the ring, FDS 20612.27-.31, taken from 2° above the ring plane.

FIGURE 1.4. A mosaic of NA edge-on views of the ring in backscatter, FDS 20630.20-.52, running two-thirds of the way from the ansa to the Jovian limb.

FIGURE 1.5. A WA edge-on view of the ring in backscatter, FDS 20630.53, capturing the same field as the previous NA mosaic. Scattered light from Jupiter, just beyond the field at lower right, saturates the corner. Fourth-magnitude star ρ Leo is visible near the frame's center.

.40, .44). The satellite Adrastea, which orbits near the ring's outer boundary, was discovered in both the NA frame FDS 20630.48 and the final WA view (Jewitt et al., 1979).

The remaining set of images was taken from within Jupiter's shadow and about 2° below the ring plane. These frames provide the most useful constraints on ring structure and composition. First, four WA images were taken in pairs through the orange and violet filters, which capture pieces of Jupiter's ring at opposite planetary limbs (FDS 20691.27-.39; Fig. 1.6). These frames were actually intended to study the scattering of light through Jupiter's upper atmosphere, and were planned before the ring was discovered; if the Voyager 1 NA camera had missed the ring, then these would have been the discovery images, as well as the entire Voyager Jovian ring data set. These frames were followed by a mosaic of seven NA images (FDS 20692.37-3.01; Fig. 1.7), whose high intrinsic resolution is marred by smear. Finally, a WA image captured the ring ansa and a portion of the same field covered by the previous NA frames (FDS 20693.02; Fig. 1.6).

After the Jovian ring discovery, Smith et al. (1979a) also reported the ring to be barely visible in a pair of much shorter (0.96 s) exposures of Amalthea taken 42 minutes later (FDS 16369.13, 15). Even for this quite favorable viewing geometry only 0.16° below the ring plane, the ring is nearly invisible for more typical Jovian exposure times. Thus we cannot reasonably expect to find any other "accidental" ring images from the Voyager mission;

L

FIGURE 1.6. A forward-scatter WA mosaic of the ring, FDS 20691.27-.39 and 20693.02, taken from inside Jupiter's shadow.

FIGURE 1.7. The NA forward-scatter mosaic, FDS 20692.37-3.01, taken just before the WA ansa image.

it is far too faint to be seen unless intentionally searched for. Hansen (private communication, 1984) looked for the ring in some satellite-search frames, and also for its shadow across the Jovian disk, but failed to find any additional data.

1.3 OTHER OBSERVATIONS

Aside from the images, rather little additional information exists on Jupiter's ring system. Not surprisingly, it is quite difficult to detect from Earth; the ring is especially faint at the small phase angles which can be sampled, and it lies within 20 arcsec of Jupiter's bright disk. Nevertheless, some resourceful observers have managed to obtain useful measurements from the ground. Smith and Reitsema (1980) and Neugebauer et al. (1981) measured the ring's reflectance spectrum at visible and infrared wavelengths, respectively, which constrain the ring particle composition. Jewitt et al. (1981) produced a groundbased ring image which is consistent with Voyager measurements, and excludes the presence of any additional ring more than 10% as bright as the known ring system.

Some information about the ring actually predates Voyager. Pioneer 11 recorded a drop in energetic particle fluxes near its closest approach to the planet, which was inside the orbit of Amalthea (Fillius et al., 1975). A ring was proposed as a possible cause for the reduction (Acuña and Ness, 1976; see also Fillius, 1976) but, since other explanations existed, this possibility was not given serious consideration.

Several other observational constraints on the ring have taken the form of limits based on nondetections. Both the Voyager 1 radio occultation (Tyler et al., 1981) and the Voyager 2 infrared spectroscopy and radiometry (IRIS) instrument (Hanel et al., 1979) failed to detect the ring. An earth-based stellar occultation observation (Dunham et al., 1981) also met with failure. From these measurements, weak upper limits on optical depth at the various wavelengths may be established, which nevertheless rule out the presence of any Uranian-type (i.e., narrow but optically thick) rings.

Although they are quite useful as supplements, none of these measurements contain as much information as the Voyager images described above. As a result, the only upcoming prospect for a profound new understanding of the ring and its workings lies in the Galileo spacecraft, expected to orbit Jupiter in 1988 and return data for a period of two years. At this juncture we can only extract whatever information is obtainable from the data in hand, to ensure that Galileo is prepared to address the right questions.

1.4 EARLIER INTERPRETATIONS OF THE DATA

Interpretations of the Jovian ring data have evolved considerably over the years since the ring's discovery. The system's most prominent feature is the narrow ring itself, dubbed the "bright ring" by Jewitt and Danielson (1981), although it is of course only bright relative to other, even less prominent

components. According to their measurements, the ring's abrupt outer boundary is at orbital radius 129200 ± 700 km ($1.81 \pm 0.01 R_J$), and its more gradual inner boundary is ~ 1500 km ($0.02 R_J$) wide, centered at 122800 ± 700 km ($1.72 \pm 0.01 R_J$). Image smear severely restricts the accuracy attainable. From the edge-on discovery view, the ring appears to be less than 30 km thick (Smith et al., 1979a).

Photometric measurements from the NA mosaic FDS 20692.37-.57 reveal scattering behavior consistent with particles of radius $r = 2 \mu\text{m}$ (Jewitt and Danielson, 1981), although diffraction naturally highlights micron-sized particles at this lighting angle. Tyler et al. (1981) determine an optical depth τ at $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength to be 3.6×10^{-4} , based on measurements of the ring's backscatter intensity by Owen et al. (1979). However, this number requires some assumptions about particle sizes and properties. It is quite a bit larger than Fillius' (private communication, 1980) determination of $\tau = \text{a few} \times 10^{-6}$ from Pioneer 11 charged particle absorption data, although this latter value applies only to grains large enough ($r \gtrsim 2$ cm) to absorb 80 MeV protons.

Ground-based spectrophotometry shows a flat to reddish spectrum for the ring, much like that for Amalthea (Neugebauer et al., 1981; Smith and Reitsema, 1980). The absence of absorption features rules out water and other ices as major ring constituents; a rocky or carbonaceous composition has been inferred, though other, more exotic possibilities remain (Burns et al., 1984).

All previous investigators have noted the presence of some additional scattered light inward from the ring's nominal boundaries (Smith et al., 1979b, Owen et al., 1979, Jewitt and Danielson, 1981). This extra brightness is apparent in every image taken at high phase angles (FDS 20691.27-3.02). It has been thought to indicate that a continuous disk of material extends from the bright ring's inner edge all the way down to the planet's cloudtops. Jewitt and Danielson (1981) report that the disk's mean brightness is roughly one-fourth that of the main ring.

Finally, Jewitt and Danielson (1981) were the first to recognize that a third component is present, a vertically-extended cloud of material which envelopes the entire system; this they named the "halo." They describe it as crudely lens-shaped, arising at the bright ring and growing rapidly to a $\sim 10^4$ km thickness inward, where it eventually reaches the planet. They also measure a small but possibly-significant ~ 300 km vertical offset between its symmetry plane and the ring. Figure 1.8, based on their Figure 5, shows enhancements of WA ansa image FDS 20693.02, revealing the three ring system components. This morphology will be critically examined in Chapter 3.

Two small satellites, Adrastea (1979J1) and Metis (1979J2), are known to reside near or within the Jovian ring. Synnott (1984) reports their orbital radii as 128980 km (1.8064 R_J) and 127960 km (1.7922 R_J), respectively. Thus Adrastea is located very close to the ring's outer boundary, while Metis is embedded within

FIGURE 1.8. The three traditional components of Jupiter's ring system, shown through enhancement of FDS 20693.02.

- a) The bright ring
- b) The inner disk
- c) The halo

the ring. The former moon is 25 ± 5 km in diameter (Jewitt, 1982), while the latter is slightly larger, ~ 40 km (Synnott, 1981). Their connection with the ring itself will be examined further in Chapter 4.

1.5 THEORETICAL MODELS

It is clear at the outset that this ring must be maintained in some steady-state manner, if it is to be a long-term feature of the Solar System. A ring composed exclusively of micron-sized particles would be quickly destroyed by any of numerous processes. Poynting-Robertson drag, plasma drag, and perhaps magnetic perturbations would rapidly disperse the grains. Of these, plasma drag seems to dominate, acting on timescales of $\sim 200 \cdot (r/\mu\text{m})$ yr (Burns et al., 1984), for grains of radius r . However, this value is uncertain to perhaps a factor of ten, due to the unknown plasma density and temperature in the ring's neighborhood; the value used here is obtained by extrapolating inward from measurements near Io. For comparison, Poynting-Robertson drag acts on timescales of $\sim 10^5 \cdot (r/\mu\text{m})$ yr. Simultaneously, sputtering and micrometeoroid impacts may destroy the particles where they sit, though on somewhat longer timescales than plasma drag. Burns et al. estimate sputtering lifetimes of $10^{3 \pm 1} \cdot (r/\mu\text{m})$ yr (assuming silicate grain composition), and meteoroid erosion lifetimes of $10^{5 \pm 1} \cdot (r/\mu\text{m})^{-2}$ yr.

For the ring to persist, new particles must continually appear to replace those lost. Most theoretical models call for a

population of larger, unseen parent bodies to be residing within the bright ring (Burns et al., 1980; Grün et al., 1980), dubbed "moons" by Burns et al. Impacts into these parent bodies from micrometeoroids, other ring particles or (possibly) Io-derived dust will give birth to the visible, micron-sized grains (Morfill et al., 1980a-d; Burns et al., 1980, 1984). Burns et al. (1984) estimate that micrometeoroid impacts alone are sufficient to maintain the bright ring, while Grün et al. (1980) hypothesize that dust is able to escape from volcanic plumes on Io, diffuse inward and impact the same moons.

In the energetic plasma environment near Jupiter, particles will reach an equilibrium surface potential, such that the net current to them is zero. Early investigators (Burns et al., 1980; Morfill et al., 1980a; see also Burns et al., 1984) had assumed surface potentials of $\Phi \approx -10$ V for ring grains. For the corresponding charge $q = \Phi r$ on micron-sized particles, Jupiter's 10° -inclined magnetic field would exert a rather strong orbital perturbation, rapidly lifting them out of the ring plane (Consolmagno, 1980, 1983; Schaffer and Burns, 1984). This is definitely not seen in the bright ring, which is less than 30 km thick (in backscatter). More recent investigators (Goertz and Ip, 1984; Havnes et al., 1984; Grün et al., 1984) have pointed out that interparticle shielding may reduce surface potentials considerably. However, the efficacy of this mechanism depends strongly upon the values of several unknown parameters, including properties

of the local plasma environment and the ring's as-yet unresolved thickness. Nevertheless, some process must reduce the charges on the bright ring grains, and shielding is a plausible mechanism.

The Jovian halo is another matter entirely; magnetic perturbations on charged grains likely explain the halo's large vertical extent. Here the dust grains are more widely separated, so shielding is apparently ineffective. The halo grains may also be smaller than those in the bright ring (Grün et al., 1980; Burns et al., 1980, 1984), which would further enhance the magnetic field's potency as a perturber. In the model of Burns et al., the halo is composed of particles decaying inward from the bright ring under drag forces, while being steadily eroded by sputtering. Once they cross the ring's inner boundary and out of its shielding, charge is quickly acquired and the magnetic field takes over. Integrations of charged grain trajectories in Jupiter's complex inner magnetic field (Consolmagno, 1983; Schaffer and Burns, 1984) show that a single grain can wander throughout the entire halo region.

Thus, some aspects of the dynamical processes in Jupiter's ring system seem to be comprehensible, although alternative models might also be constructed. New observational constraints on the system are needed before the theories discussed above may be either refined or disproved.

CHAPTER 2

INTERPRETING VOYAGER IMAGES

2.1 IMAGE DATA AND PROCESSING

The Voyager imaging experiment consists of two vidicon camera systems which, along with other instruments, are mounted on each spacecraft's steerable scan platform (Danielson et al., 1981). The cameras have fields of view of 0.43° (NA) and 3.18° (WA). Each vidicon holds a square array of picture elements (pixels), with 800 samples per line and 800 lines. Lines increase downward in the frame, while samples increase from left to right. The light measured by the vidicon's photosensitive surface within the field of each pixel is assigned a data number (DN) from 0 to 255, and these DNs are then transmitted back to Earth in digital form. Hence each raw Voyager image consists of an 800×800 array of integers. A color filter wheel is attached to each camera, allowing limited spectral resolution.

Extensive reprocessing is needed on the ground before quantitative conclusions may be drawn from these images. First, a "dark current," or Voyager image of dark sky, is subtracted from the raw frame. The primary purpose of this step is to counter the tendency of the DNs to increase during image readout even with the shutter closed. Without this step, each image would brighten from top to

bottom, since lower lines are read out last.

Next the DNs are converted to absolute intensities, based upon the measured light response of each pixel. The vidicons have been calibrated both on the ground and in flight, as described by Danielson et al. (1981). It is generally more convenient to discuss intensities in units of I/F , where F is the incident solar flux density. Since F already contains all properties of the incident solar light, including its spectrum, only the scattering properties of the target body determine this ratio.

Finally, it is often useful to geometrically correct an image, since both the camera optics and vidicons have inherent distortion. The actual image geometry is determined from an array of reseau markings which are etched on the vidicon faceplate. The geometric correction ("geom") process is a reprojection onto a new 1000×1000 pixel grid, so that the reseau markings have their proper relative locations. In published photographs, reseau markings are often removed for cosmetic purposes by replacing them with an average of the surrounding pixels. Thus they are not usually visible in processed frames, except where they fall atop abrupt intensity transitions.

The processing described above gives results which are adequate for most Voyager image analysis. However, the Jovian ring data set, consisting of very long exposures of low intensity features, is especially susceptible to any calibration errors which may arise. The raw data itself has several limitations. Images of

a uniform field will always show some random variation among DNs, due to random noise in the camera and electronics. Systematic errors of several sorts also appear. On occasion, the vidicon tube does not completely reset between frames, so the ghost of a previous image remains visible, albeit faintly, in a new frame. Ghost images can always be recognized by simply checking the content of the previous frame taken on the same camera. A more common problem found in the faint Jovian ring images is scattered light. Bright sources just outside the field of view sometimes scatter light into the camera optics, which pollutes the frame. This is perfectly analogous to the difficulty of observing Amalthea from the ground, where light from the bright Jovian disk must somehow be eliminated. The distribution of scattered light across an image is usually smooth; although it elevates the overall noise level, it may usually be subtracted from abruptly-bounded features. However, it can make diffuse structures, such as the Jovian halo, nearly impossible to recognize.

The camera system's light response and dark current can vary rather significantly during each planetary encounter; Jupiter's intense radiation environment especially enhances these variations. To partially compensate for this, dark current frames were taken occasionally during each encounter. However, it is standard practice at JPL's Image Processing Laboratory to use only a single standard dark current for each camera, spacecraft and planet, and for each of the few discrete image readout rates. Subtraction of a

less appropriate dark current generally introduces a nonzero offset and/or a smooth gradient to the background level in a frame. In appearance this is not unlike the scattered light contribution. It may be partially eliminated if instead the dark current frame taken closest in time to the image of interest is used; all of our data have been reprocessed in this manner.

As a final correction, we often fit a smooth function (a quadratic or line and sample) to the background light in our images, and subtract. Background light may be measured anywhere in a frame that is devoid of visible features, such as blank sky or the dark side of Jupiter. This processing corrects for error arising from inadequacy of the dark current frame, as well as for scattered light. Despite this improvement, the zero intensity level of an image remains uncertain. It is always preferable to reference an intensity measurement to a nearby dark sky region, if one is available.

The absolute calibration of the Voyager cameras is another source of uncertainty. Danielson et al. (1981) determined correction factors to be applied to Voyager image intensities, as a function of spacecraft, planet, camera and filter. However, discrepancies still persist between Voyager- and Earth-based photometry of the Jovian and Saturnian satellites. New correction factors have recently been determined, though not yet published (Buratti, private communication, 1984). In the end, absolute calibration of the Voyager cameras must be regarded as uncertain at

the level of a few percent, although comparisons between images, particularly those taken a short time apart through the same camera and filter, should be consistent to much better accuracy.

2.2 SPATIAL RESOLUTION

Spatial resolution is a widely-misunderstood concept in planetary image analysis. Ideally, it should be a reliable measure of the scale in an image on which detail may be recognized. As a simple-minded first step, we can quantify the dimension of each pixel, as it is projected to the distance of the target body; hence, one might describe the resolution of an image in terms of kilometers per pixel; these values have been listed in Table 2.1.

However, we have no guarantee that individual pixels in the data are actually resolved. For example, if the camera were out of focus, then a point source would blur out to occupy several pixels. Additionally, geometric correction involves reprojecting the original 800^2 pixels onto a slightly finer 1000^2 grid; we know intuitively that such a process, in itself, certainly does not improve image detail.

In some discussions of digital images, resolution is quoted in terms of kilometers per "line pair" rather than per pixel. This designation refers back to a measurement of resolution on photographic film; it corresponds to the width (i.e., wavelength) of the narrowest possible pattern of alternate black and white stripes which could be reliably distinguished on the film. In the case of

TABLE 2.1: Jovian Ring Image Resolution and Smear

FDS	Resolution (km/pixel) ^b	Smear (pixels) ^b		
		Star	Voyager	Sum
16368.19	9.5	193 ^a	482	294
20612.27	15.7	31	47-50	69-72
20612.31	15.7	15	50	60
20630.24	11.0	118	97	197
20630.28	11.0	50	98	69
20630.32	11.0	49	98	71
20630.36	11.0	25	99	82
20630.40	11.0	30	99	82
20630.44	11.0	?	100	?
20630.48	10.9	45	101	77
20630.52	10.9	101	104	190
20630.53	81.8	<2	2.2	<4
20691.27	88.2	4	10-12	14-15
20691.31	88.4	11 ^a	10-12	20-22
20691.35	88.5	7	10-11	17-18
20691.39	88.6	23 ^a	10-11	11-13
20692.37	12.1	105	66-75	31-40
20692.41	12.1	65	66-74	5-11
20692.45	12.1	?	65-72	?
20692.49	12.1	28	65-71	90-96
20692.53	12.2	35	65-70	97-101
20692.57	12.2	82 ^a	66-69	100-102
20693.01	12.2	34 ^a	70	?
20693.02	91.3	<1	1.5	<2.5

^aStar trails are not straight lines.

^bPixels here refer to those in geometrically corrected images.

digital images, this becomes somewhat more complex. Imagine an image of black and white stripes taken such that a black stripe precisely fills one row of pixels, while its neighboring white stripe fills the next row. Such an image would show the black and white stripes just as desired. However, if the stripes were displaced by half a pixel, then each pixel would contain half black and half white, so the digital image would appear a uniform gray; the stripes would not be resolved at all. To allow for this, and also for other possible stripe orientations with respect to the pixel grid, the "line pair" resolution of a digital image is generally designated as $2\sqrt{2}$ times the pixel dimension (NASA, 1980). Line pairs of this size could be reliably distinguished, regardless of their position and orientation in a digital image.

It should be noted therefore that the word "line" in "line pair" does not have the same origin or meaning as that in the Voyager vidicon's "lines" of pixels. Nevertheless, to avoid unnecessary confusion over the years, line pair has come to mean a pair of pixel lines in Voyager images, and so differs by a factor of 2, not $2\sqrt{2}$, from the pixel resolution.

At this point, it should be obvious that any definition of resolution is to some extent arbitrary. Whether a feature in a planetary image is resolved depends to some extent on what sort of feature it is. Its orientation, shape and brightness variation will all play a role. For consistency and simplicity, we will always designate the resolution of an image in terms of km/pixel.

However, we must also understand the quality of our image data if we wish to know what scale of visible structure can be believed. We will define a "resolution cell" as the area within an image over which intensity values correlate; image features separated by distances greater than the dimension of a cell are independent and therefore, in some sense, resolved. The cell cannot be smaller than a pixel, and may be considerably larger. This is analogous to grain size on photographic film; it is therefore smaller by a rough factor of two than the canonical "line pair."

It is not especially useful to know the resolution characteristics for the original raw frames, because we would then be left with the difficult and uncertain task of propagating them through the multistep processing (which introduces errors of its own). Instead, it is simpler and more direct to study the data in hand, and let it demonstrate its own reliability.

Because it is difficult to distinguish pixel correlations introduced by the camera and subsequent processing from those which are simply part of the field being photographed, we consider two specific situations. First, we study the correlations within a uniform image field, where intensity variations may be ascribed to noise alone. Most of this noise arises in the imaging system's electronics, and so is independent of any flaws in the camera optics. The most obvious source of noise correlations in a blank field is the geom process, in which each new pixel becomes a

weighted average of the four nearest pixels in the original grid. Second, we study the camera's response to an unresolved light source (e.g., an unsmearred star), which does not bypass the camera optics. This provides a direct measure of the image scale on which structure is not resolved. It is analogous to the point-spread function measurements of Benesh and Jepsen (1978).

To study noise correlations in an image field, we regard each pixel intensity I_i as a random variable. In a uniform field, these variables all have the same mean \bar{I} and variance σ^2 , but non-zero correlations. These correlations ρ should only be functions of the distance $d = (\delta l^2 + \delta s^2)^{1/2}$ separating the pixels, where δl and δs are the offsets in line and sample. We will designate the distance between the i^{th} and j^{th} pixels by d_{ij} , which can take on only discrete values (0, 1, $\sqrt{2}$, 2, $\sqrt{5}$, $2\sqrt{2}$, 3, etc.).

Parameters of the probability distributions for the I_i may be expressed in terms of expectation values:

$$\bar{I} = \langle I_i \rangle ; \quad [2.1]$$

$$\sigma^2 = \langle (I_i - \bar{I})^2 \rangle ; \quad [2.2]$$

$$\rho(d_{ij}) = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \langle (I_i - \bar{I}) \cdot (I_j - \bar{I}) \rangle . \quad [2.3]$$

As defined in [2.3], ρ equals 1 for perfect correlation, 0 for no correlation and -1 for perfect anticorrelation. Reasonable

estimators of these values may now be defined in terms of averages over the sample population. An unbiased estimate of the sample mean is

$$\hat{I} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i I_i , \quad [2.4]$$

where N is the number of pixels sampled. Estimators for the variance and correlation are

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (I_i - \hat{I})^2 \quad [2.5]$$

and

$$\hat{\rho}(d) = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}^2} \frac{1}{N(d)} \sum_{d_{ij}=d} (I_i - \hat{I}) \cdot (I_j - \hat{I}) . \quad [2.6]$$

The sum in [2.6] is over all pixel pairs separated by distance d , where $N(d)$ is the number of such pairs. These estimators can be shown to have biases which are of order $1/N$, which is negligible for a sufficiently large sample. Note that [2.5] cannot be made unbiased by replacing N by $N-1$, as is normally the case, because the individual I -values correlate.

We have tabulated $\hat{\rho}$ as a function of pixel separation d for flat 20×20 regions in many of the Jovian ring images. With $N =$

400, any biases in the estimators are $\lesssim 1\%$, and may be neglected for our purposes. No significant variation in $\hat{\rho}(d)$ has been detected between fields or even between WA and NA images; this may be due to the fact that most correlations arise in the geom step, which is quite similar for both WA and NA frames. Fig. 2.1 is a plot of the correlation, averaged over all images. The full width at half-power for $\hat{\rho}(d)$ is ~ 1.6 pixels, so this will be one estimate of the nominal resolution cell size, applicable to all of the images studied.

Examination of stars provides a more direct measure of Voyager image resolution. An unsmeared star is effectively a delta-function light source, its angular extent in the image only the result of imperfect camera response, binning into finite pixels and subsequent image processing. Even a smeared star should appear as an infinitesimally narrow line segment, smeared by the change in the camera's pointing direction, but broadened perpendicular to that only by the reasons mentioned above.

We have measured a total of 11 star profiles, from a number of the Jovian ring images studied. Overall, the WA images show star widths of 2.4 ± 0.2 pixels, while the NA images show 2.2 ± 0.2 , which is insignificantly smaller. These represent full widths at half maximum; in general, a star's light drops from its maximum into the background noise in an equal distance. These measurements are relatively independent of star image intensity and smear, except for the very brightest stars, which saturate in the middle

FIGURE 2.1. A plot of estimated DN correlations $\hat{\rho}$ between pixels in Voyager images, as a function of the distance d separating them. The error bars are the standard deviations in our measurements. The dashed line is simply a smooth fit to the data.

and show broader profiles. Reassuringly, these numbers are only slightly larger than the previous measurement, which refers primarily to broadening introduced in the geometric correction.

2.3 INTENSITY MEASUREMENTS

A Voyager intensity measurement \hat{I} is generally obtained by averaging over a set of N contiguous pixels, as is shown in [2.4]. This may be regarded as an unbiased estimator of the true intensity \bar{I} , and it is useful to know the uncertainty in our estimate. This requires an estimate of the variance in \hat{I} :

$$\text{var}(\hat{I}) = \langle (\hat{I} - \bar{I})^2 \rangle . \quad [2.7]$$

Substituting [2.4] into [2.7] above yields

$$\text{var}(\hat{I}) = \frac{1}{N^2} \langle \sum_i \sum_j (I_i - \bar{I}) \cdot (I_j - \bar{I}) \rangle . \quad [2.8]$$

Here the expectation value is simply a sum of covariances, so comparison with [2.3] leads to

$$\text{var}(\hat{I}) = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_i \sum_j \sigma^2 \cdot \rho(d_{ij}) . \quad [2.9]$$

The summation may be split into $i=j$ and $i \neq j$ components:

$$\text{var}(\hat{I}) = \frac{\sigma^2}{N^2} \left[\sum_i \rho(0) + \sum_{i \neq j} \rho(d_{ij}) \right] \quad [2.10]$$

or, finally,

$$\text{var}(\hat{I}) = \frac{\sigma^2}{N} \left[1 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i \neq j} \rho(d_{ij}) \right]. \quad [2.11]$$

Thus, for uncorrelated pixels, the measurement variance is simply σ^2 reduced by the factor of $1/N$. By [2.11], an estimate of the variance in \hat{I} is arrived at by replacing σ^2 and ρ by $\hat{\sigma}^2$ and $\hat{\rho}$. In a large region, nearly every sampled pixel has its nearest neighbors included in the set. Hence,

$$\sum_{i \neq j} \hat{\rho}(d_{ij}) = N[4\hat{\rho}(1) + 4\hat{\rho}(\sqrt{2}) + 4\hat{\rho}(2) + 8\hat{\rho}(2\sqrt{2}) + \dots] \quad [2.12]$$

which, by the values in Fig. 2.1, equals $2.2N$. Thus,

$$\text{var}(\hat{I}) = 3.2 \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{N} \quad [2.13]$$

For analysis purposes, we designate $3.2\hat{\sigma}^2$ as the single-pixel variance in the image, and then estimate our uncertainties from the standard $1/N$ reduction factor. The noise level in an image depends primarily on camera, filter, exposure time and readout rate; it is

generally uniform across a single frame. Thus, for those averages in which N is small, we use a reference noise level measured elsewhere in the frame.

The factor of 3.2 may be easily understood in qualitative terms. Each pixel in a geomed image is a weighted average of the four nearest pixels in the original data, which are nearly uncorrelated. The weighting factors are determined from the amount that each pixel in the new, geometrically correct grid overlaps the original, distorted grid. This average artificially reduces the apparent noise in an image. Equally-weighted averaging would reduce the variance by precisely a factor of four; unequal weights reduce it slightly less. The factor of 3.2 which we determine is a quite plausible mean value.

2.4 IMAGE GEOMETRY

To interpret a spacecraft image, it is important to know the geometry of the field in view. For example, we might wish to determine the location (i.e., latitude and longitude) of a planetary surface feature, or the radius of a visible ring. Once the image itself has been geometrically corrected, this is a straightforward matter.

The parameters which make this interpretation possible are the spacecraft location and camera orientation when the exposure was taken. This information is cataloged in the Supplementary Experiment Data Record (SEDR), which accompanies each Voyager

image. A complete description of procedures for calculating image geometry is found in Appendix A.

As elsewhere, geometric interpretations are fraught with difficulties, most of which arise from uncertainties in the necessary parameters. In particular, the Voyager scan platform is generally able to point the cameras to an accuracy of 0.1-0.2°, roughly one-third of the NA field of view. Pointing uncertainties are even larger in the forward-scattered exposures of Jupiter's ring, when the spacecraft was in Jupiter's shadow and could not orient itself to the Sun. Thus the camera's pointing must be corrected before image geometry can be understood. This correction may be determined from the image location of a known reference, such as a star, satellite, planetary limb or ring of known radius. Stars provide the most reliable reference, and they are often visible in the Jovian ring images, which tend to be long exposures containing large regions of dark sky. Consequently, we now understand the geometry of nearly every Jovian ring image to the level of a few pixels or better. The pointing references we have used in each image are summarized in Table 2.2.

The precise Voyager trajectories past Jupiter are also slightly uncertain; the Voyager Navigation Team estimates uncertainties of < 10-15 km for Voyager 1 and < 20-30 km for Voyager 2 (Campbell, private communication, 1984). This introduces uncertainties to any measured image location of the same magnitude. These errors cannot be readily corrected, but they are quite tiny.

TABLE 2.2: Pointing References in the Jovian Ring Images

FDS	Object ^a	Location	
		Line	Sample
16368.19	SAO 098010	720	675
	SAO 098013	665	685
	SAO 098014	660	655
	SAO 098018	500	580
	SAO 098019	605	190
	SAO 098020	370	900
	SAO 098021	370	860
	SAO 098024	415	585
	SAO 098032	150	580
20612.27	9h18m51s/13°57'30"	390	485
	9h19m13s/14° 3' 0"	165	645
20612.31	9h17m 7s/13°55m 0"	695	550
20630.24	SAO 099106	715	810
20630.28	SAO 099136	530	250
	SAO 099138	315	385
20630.32	SAO 118325	730	450
20630.36	SAO 118325	670	730
20630.40	SAO 118325	895	730
20630.44	ring		
20630.48	SAO 118352	360	400
20630.52	SAO 118355	660	890
	10h30m27s/9°30'30"	665	670
	10h31m 0s/9°43'45"	95	740
20630.53	SAO 118355	530	545
	SAO 118380	580	295
	SAO 118418	325	65
20691.27	ring, limb		
20691.31	ring, limb		
20691.35	SAO 164430 ring, limb	700	945

TABLE 2.2: (continued)

FDS	Object ^a	Location	
		Line	Sample
20691.39	SAO 164430 ring, limb	700	955
20692.37	SAO 164477 ring	745	595
20692.41	21h31m39s/-13°10'15" ring	525	280
20692.45	ring		
20692.49	SAO 164527 ring	265	260
20692.53	SAO 164557 ring	485	690
20692.57	21h37m41s/-12°46'00" 21h37m40s/-12°40'30"	230	470
		410	440
20693.01	SAO 164584	350	430
	SAO 164594	835	730
	SAO 164596	945	770
20693.02	SAO 164539	85	250
	SAO 164557	365	335
	SAO 164562	910	335
	SAO 164576	920	405
	SAO 164584	485	500
	SAO 164616	935	640
	SAO 164618	640	660
	SAO 164627	345	750

^aStars are listed by their SAO catalog number when available; uncataloged stars are designated by their right ascension and declination, as measured from the Palomar plates. For each star, its approximate location on the geomed image is also listed.

Smear is a more formidable geometry problem. This arises from two sources: first, any wobble in the precise pointing direction of the camera during an exposure; and second, Voyager's changing perspective on a target at finite distance as the spacecraft moves along its trajectory. The first term is apparent from the long, sometimes kinked, trails left in an image by stars (see for example the discovery image, Fig. 1.1). The second term decreases inversely with the distance to the target body, and so vanishes entirely for stars. The two components must be added vectorially to yield the correct smear; they are often comparable in magnitude, though different in direction. Smear may usually be neglected for the typical few-second or less exposures of brighter bodies at Jupiter and Saturn, but is especially prominent in the long exposures we study. Nevertheless, from visible star trails and Voyager's known motion during an exposure, the smearing of an image may be understood. Appendix A contains a discussion of smear in rigorous mathematical terms. Table 2.1 lists the amount of smear in each image.

It is possible, at least in principle, to "desmear" a digital image if the precise smearing is known. The smeared image may be understood as the convolution of the unflawed image with a point-response function; desmearing is therefore the inverse, deconvolution process. It involves taking the two-dimensional Fourier Transform (FT) of the image, dividing by the FT of the point response function, and transforming back. Filtering at various

stages along the way is needed to compensate for the effects of noise. Desmearing therefore requires extensive, time-consuming and costly numerical computations. Haemmerle et al. (1982) attempted this for the forward-scattered NA mosaic, in which smear is most troublesome. However, since they used only the star-trail component of smear, their results were unsatisfactory. Synnott (1984) states that he is now attempting a correct desmearing. For our purposes, a precise knowledge of the smearing in each image has proved to approach the usefulness of clean, unsmearred data.

2.5 PHOTOMETRY

From the intensity of light scattered by Jupiter's ring system, we wish to infer properties of the constituent particles. Three photometric quantities are of particular interest: normal optical depth τ , single-scattering albedo $\tilde{\omega}_0$ and phase function $P(\theta)$, where θ is the scattering angle, measured from the direction of the incident sunlight. Phase function P is normalized, so that it averages to unity when integrated over all solid angles.

These quantities are related to measured intensity by

$$\frac{I}{F} = \frac{\tau \tilde{\omega}_0 P(\theta)}{4\mu} \quad [2.14]$$

(Cuzzi et al., 1984, Appendix) where $\mu = |\cos \epsilon|$, and ϵ is the emission angle, defined as the angle between the ring plane normal on the sunward side and the spacecraft direction. Thus the product

$\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$, in which each factor has a direct physical interpretation, can be determined with no restrictive assumptions about individual particle properties. It is also independent of all geometric projection effects, thereby facilitating the comparison of measurements from different images. All that is required for [2.14] to be valid is that multiple scattering be ignorable, which is the case provided the line-of-sight optical depth τ/μ is small. This is known to be true for all of our images, except for a brief period during FDS 16368.19, as Voyager passed through the ring plane (where, for an instant, $\mu = 0$).

For an extended cloud of material, such as the Jovian halo, it is more useful to consider light-scattering as a function of distance along the line of sight, rather than integrated through the ring plane. We replace the normal optical depth τ by the linear extinction coefficient α , which simply represents optical depth per unit distance. If this quantity is constant along a line of sight of length d , then [2.14] becomes

$$\frac{I}{F} = \frac{\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0P(\theta)}{4} \cdot d . \quad [2.15]$$

This expression still assumes that the line-of-sight optical depth αd is small.

In discussions of photometry, we will make frequent use of the size parameter X , which is the ratio of particle circumference

$2\pi r$ to the wavelength λ . Under many plausible circumstances, light-scattering properties are dependent on this single dimensionless parameter, rather than on the size and wavelength separately. In effect, the light's wavelength acts as the "yardstick" by which each particle is measured, so that, for example, doubling both will leave the scattering properties unchanged. This fact can be quite useful, particularly when comparing photometry taken through different color filters.

Ring particle sizes may be described by a distribution function $n(r)$, defined such that $n(r)dr$ is the number of particles per unit ring area in the size range from r to $r + dr$. Given a size distribution and refractive index, and assuming spherical grains, it is possible to predict the light scattered into any direction by the distribution, as is discussed in Appendix B. Unfortunately, the inverse is not true; intensities from a limited range of scattering angles cannot be uniquely inverted to give unambiguous particle properties. This fact must be kept in mind in any attempt to interpret photometry.

CHAPTER 3

GROSS MORPHOLOGY: THE THREE COMPONENTS RECONSIDERED

Since 1980, the Jovian ring system has been widely believed to be composed of the three rather distinct components, first identified by Jewitt and Danielson (1981) as the bright ring, disk and halo. Fig. 3.1 is a sketch of this model, both in cross section and as it might reasonably appear from a vantage point a few degrees out of the ring plane above Jupiter's unlit face. Note in particular the abrupt cutoff of the ring and disk as they cross the planet's shadow boundary. In this highly foreshortened view, the entire radial extent of the system is compressed onto the dashed line from the limb at $1.0 R_J$ to the bright ring at $1.8 R_J$. This dashed line represents the intersection of the ring plane with Jupiter's crudely cylindrical shadow boundary.

In Figs. 3.2 and 3.3 we present enhanced versions of FDS 20693.02 and 20691.35, frames which together comprise a view quite similar to that diagrammed in Fig. 3.1b. Voyager's viewing geometry has been depicted in Fig. 1.2. These figures are produced by replacing a range of intensities in the images with discrete shades of gray; boundaries between different shades therefore represent isophotes as measured by Voyager. The ansa image (Fig. 3.2) clearly shows a vertically-extended halo which arises just inside the bright ring.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 3.1. A sketch of the Jewitt and Danielson (1981) model of the Jovian ring system, showing the ring, disk and lenticular halo.

(a) The system as seen in cross section.

(b) The system as viewed from slightly out of the ring plane. The planet's shadow intersects the ring plane at the dashed line.

FIGURE 3.2. An enhancement of FDS 20693.02, showing the halo material in shades of gray. The boundary lines between shades correspond to isophotes in the image.

FIGURE 3.3. An enhancement of FDS 20691.35, showing the halo material in shades of gray. The shading scheme is identical to that in Fig. 3.2.

The limb image (Fig. 3.3), however, seems less compatible with the ring/disk/halo model. The bright ring can be clearly seen to vanish as it crosses the shadow and its illumination is occulted. However the disk, reported to be one-fourth as bright as this ring, does not show a cutoff of the expected form. Despite ~18 pixels of smear in this image, such a brightness transition should be observable, as isophotes roughly parallel to the predicted cutoff line (shown dashed in Fig. 3.1b).

The intensity contours in this region have a very different character, running parallel to the limb and concentrated just inside the bright ring. Additional "bumps" in the isophotes, still running along a line parallel to the Jovian limb, continue well above the ring's far arm in the figure. The three other images of the shadow boundary (FDS 20691.27, .31, .39) show a similar arrangement of contours. These characteristics suggest that we are seeing the Jovian shadow projected on a radially-confined, vertically-extended cloud; it prompts our revised model of the ring system morphology, sketched in Fig. 3.4. In this view, no disk is present at all; we ascribe the interior scattered light noted by all previous investigators to overlapping arms of a (crudely) toroidal halo, as seen on the right side of the sketch. The halo diagrammed is similar to the previous model, except for its finite radial extent, ceasing roughly halfway between the ring and Jupiter's cloudtops. Such a system is substantially more compatible with the isophotes near the limb, while those near the ansa fit either model equally well.

FIGURE 3.4. A sketch of our model for the Jovian ring system, to be compared to Fig. 3.1. The ring circumscribes a crudely toroidal halo; no disk is present.

(a) The system as seen in cross section.

(b) The system as viewed from slightly out of the ring plane.

Although we feel that there is no longer any reason to believe a disk is present, the subject's history compels us to place an upper limit on a disk intensity. We do so by averaging intensities along lines parallel to the shadow's hypothetical intersection with the ring plane, in the region between the planetary limb and the main ring (Fig. 3.5). We plot these intensities as a function of an arbitrary scan variable which increases upward through the ring plane, so that the disk should become illuminated suddenly at the scan value where the boundary is crossed. One such scan is shown in Fig. 3.6. However, smear during the 96 s exposure shifts the shadow line by a small but known (~10 pixel) distance on the images, yielding instead a range of scan values over which the disk should come into view. We then measure the amount by which intensity increases in this range, and call this an upper limit on the disk intensity. In truth, the halo is brightening monotonically across this region, so the value we measure is probably due to the halo alone. Nevertheless, this conservative upper limit, derived from scans on all four of the limb images, is $I/F < 2-4 \times 10^{-6}$, or 1% of the bright ring's intensity.

The disk designation appears to have been simply a historical accident, since the presence of interior scattered light had been noted long before the out-of-plane halo was discovered (Smith et al., 1979b). It is also an observational accident, since any view from somewhat farther out of the ring plane would have separated the halo arms and not suggested a continuous sheet.

FIGURE 3.5. A sketch of the disk constraint technique, drawn for image FDS 20691.35. Every pixel which falls within the dashed region has its intensity binned as a function of parameter x , which varies from 0 to 1. Coordinates x_1 and x_2 fall at the initial and final locations of the ring/shadow intersection.

FIGURE 3.6. An intensity trace measured from FDS 20691.27. The smear range and corresponding I/F limit are shown.

From the theoretical point of view, the disk component had always been the most difficult to understand. Burns et al. (1980) argued that tiny grains drawn inward from the ring by drag forces would be too small to be held in a thin disk; Jupiter's inclined magnetic field would quickly perturb them out of the plane and into the halo. They offered the unsatisfying ad hoc proposal that some macroscopic parent bodies were present in the disk, though fewer than in the bright ring. However, realizing that light scattered by the halo might give the appearance of a disk, they also questioned the disk's existence; at the time they did not test this possibility.

Perhaps Fig. 3.4b is somewhat misleading in its crude portrayal of the halo as a uniform torus. In fact, the isophote distribution, by its greatest concentration just inside the bright ring, indicates that the halo particle density is greatest for a dense core just inside the ring, and then drops off quickly with decreasing radius and increasing elevation. The halo inner boundary is not abrupt, but simply the rough location where it becomes too faint to be seen. We present in Chapter 5 a more refined determination of halo structure, demonstrating further the diagnostic value of the shadow boundary.

CHAPTER 4

FINE STRUCTURE IN THE BRIGHT JOVIAN RING

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Jupiter's bright ring has been described by Jewitt and Danielson (1981) as of roughly uniform brightness, with an abrupt outer boundary (decaying over < 700 km) at radius 129000 ± 700 km ($1.81 \pm 0.01 R_J$). Its inner boundary is more gradual, decaying over ~ 1500 km, and is centered at 122000 ± 700 km ($1.72 \pm 0.01 R_J$), where the ring fades into the halo. These investigators also confirm the presence of the narrow, bright annulus first reported by Owen et al. (1979), centered at roughly 127800 km ($1.79 R_J$), and about 10% brighter in forward-scattered light than the surrounding ring. Jewitt (1982) reports that this same annulus is $\sim 50\%$ brighter than the main ring in backscattered light.

It is interesting to compare the above radial distances with the orbits Synnott (1984) has determined for the ring's two known embedded satellites. Adrastea has a semimajor axis of 128980 km ($1.8064 R_J$), close to the outer boundary. Metis is at 127960 km ($1.7922 R_J$), near the bright annulus. Eccentricity is poorly-constrained for Adrastea, and is less than 4×10^{-3} for Metis. One is tempted to draw dynamical associations between the satellites and the nearby features, as Burns et al. (1980, 1984) have tried to

do, but the ~ 700 km error bars are large enough to make any physical ties uncertain. Refining the measurements, as well as searching for additional possible structure, would shed new light on ring processes.

The intrinsic resolution of the Voyager frames is substantially finer than the ~ 700 km errors previously quoted. Table 2.1 contains these values, which range from ~ 10 to 100 km/pixel for the images of interest. The twin problems of pointing error and smear are responsible for the large uncertainties. However, as discussed in §2.4 and Appendix A, we have reduced pointing uncertainties to a few pixels or less in nearly every instance. While smear is much more difficult to compensate for, the manner in which an image has been smeared may be predicted quite accurately. For our purposes, this information is often sufficient.

4.2 MEASUREMENTS

The best combination of signal and resolution on the bright ring is found in Voyager's final view, FDS 20693.02, an image of the ansa viewed from 2° beneath the ring plane (Fig. 4.1). Radial resolution across the ansa is roughly 100 km/pixel, though the projection factor of $\sin 2^\circ = 0.03$ (due to the oblique viewing geometry) severely limits resolution elsewhere. Being a relatively brief (15.36 s) exposure through the WA camera, the image has much less smear than other frames. Also, since it was taken from within Jupiter's shadow in forward-scattered light, the ring is especially

FIGURE 4.1. Contrast enhancement of the bright ring ansa in FDS 20693.02, showing radial structure.

bright and scattered light is minimal.

We have located eight SAO catalog stars in the dark regions of this image, corresponding to every star in the field brighter than magnitude 8.5 (see Table 2.2). Many fainter stars are also visible, but can be pinpointed less reliably. Based on these locations, we have been able to correct the image's ~50-pixel pointing offset, with residual uncertainties of slightly less than one pixel, or ~30 km. Uncertainty in Voyager's position introduces an additional 20-30 km error. The stars show no evidence of smear ($< \sim 100$ km), while Voyager's motion introduces a 130-km smear component. Figure 4.2 is a radial intensity profile of the bright ring, based on a narrow strip of pixels across the ansa in this image. It is plotted in units of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0 P(\theta)$, here with scattering angle $\theta = 6^\circ$.

In this profile several ring features are visible, notably the relatively abrupt outer boundary and the bright annulus; these features may be seen in the enhanced image itself. The halo's presence is also unmistakable, from the fact that the intensity does not drop to zero near the inner ring boundary at ~122000 km. It then begins to rise again inward from there, as lines of sight through the halo lengthen. However, moving outward, the halo contribution must drop to zero within the scan, because negligible intensity is measured outside the ring; this is the same image we used to argue that the halo is roughly bounded by the bright ring (see Fig. 3.2). The dashed line in the figure represents a rough

FIGURE 4.2. A radial profile of the bright ring, as measured from FDS 20693.02. The RMS noise amplitude is also shown.

determination of the halo's light contribution within this profile, based upon photometric considerations which will be discussed in Chapter 6.

One might have expected the NA mosaic (FDS 20692.37-.57), taken immediately before this image, to have finer radial resolution. It does not, in part because of the substantially greater smear in these longer (96 s) exposures. In addition, the aforementioned projection factor of $\sin 2^\circ$ reduces the resolution by more than the NA camera improves it. Optimal resolution might have been attained in FDS 20692.57, which captures part of the ansa and therefore avoids the projection factor, but this frame is smeared by nearly 100 pixels. Desmearing of this image offers the best hope of improved radial resolution, although the lengthy star trails (which include a right-angle bend in the middle) will make the processing difficult.

The preceding image, FDS 20692.53, holds the best resolution of the NA sequence, through a fortuitous near-cancellation of the two smear components on the upper ring arm (see Appendix A). The image is shown in Fig. 4.3, processed to enhance radial structure; the resultant profile is found in Fig. 4.4. Although the diminished resolution is apparent, it is roughly consistent with the previous scan. The bright annulus and the outer boundary fall at the same locations. Note however that in this view the halo is present throughout, and is nearly as bright as the ring itself.

Substantially greater resolution on the ring (~10 km/pixel)

FIGURE 4.3. Contrast enhancement of the bright ring's far arm in FDS 20692.53, showing radial structure.

FIGURE 4.4. Radial profile of the bright ring, as measured from FDS 20692.53.

is found in the backscattered NA sequence taken near ring plane crossing, which ended with FDS 20630.52 capturing the ring's outer terminus. Smear is an obstacle as usual, and noise is especially prominent in these frames, with the almost fully-lit Jovian disk not far from the field of view. Nevertheless, the last image should provide a good measure of the ring's outer boundary. The projection factor of $\sin(0.1^\circ) = 0.002$ makes all previous images in the sequence worthless as sources of radial information.

The ~200-pixel smear of FDS 20630.52 hinders a straightforward interpretation at first. However, the frame makes complete sense if we overlay the initial and final outlines of a 129000-km ring, shown in Fig. 4.5. These curve predictions are based upon the endpoints of three visible star trails and Voyager's known motion; they are accurate to within a few pixels. The coincidence of the curves with the smear limits of the ring provide assurance that we understand the geometry. The ring apparently smeared in a direction 13° away from parallel to itself in the image plane. Now we can effectively "desmear" the image simply by averaging across lines parallel to the net smear vector, which runs between the ansae of the plotted curves. The resultant scan is shown in Fig. 4.6. Even from this viewpoint just 0.12° below the ring plane, mutual shadowing of particles is completely negligible; for τ as large as 10^{-4} , the line of sight optical depth $\tau/\mu = 0.05$, much less than one.

In truth this particular profile is confused by a mixture of

FIGURE 4.5. Contrast enhancement of the bright ring's outer terminus in ring-plane view FDS 20630.52. Overplotted are the initial and final positions of a 129000-km ring, based on the endpoints of the star trails.

FIGURE 4.6. A radial profile of the bright ring's outer region, as measured from FDS 20630.52. The RMS noise amplitude is also shown.

radii in each particular radius bin. A line of sight associated with a specific radius actually contains some contributions from all external radii, as is diagrammed in Fig. 4.7. One consequence of this averaging is that a direct conversion to $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ is not possible, so the scan is left in units of I/F. Despite this different viewing geometry and the limited radial coverage, this profile shows much of the same structure as is found in Fig. 4.2. Note in particular the several broad "humps" in the scan; these are also visible in the contrast-enhanced image, as bright and dark lines parallel to the smear direction.

The last image with possibly-useful radial information is the first--the Jovian ring discovery frame FDS 16368.19. This is another in-plane view of the ring's outer terminus, qualitatively similar to the frame just discussed. However, the smear in this 11-minute exposure is much more difficult to model. Seven separate images of the ring appear, one very badly smeared and almost invisible, followed by six narrow, bright ones. To make matters worse, a bright star falls directly atop the ring image endpoints, and a data dropout crosses the ring just above. We show a portion of the frame in Fig. 4.8, and a sketch which serves as a key to its interpretation in Fig. 4.9.

As always, the smear of this image may be understood by describing its geometry as a function of elapsed time after the camera shutter opened. During this interval, Voyager passed from 450 km above the ring plane to 120 km below, with negligible

FIGURE 4.7. A sketch of the viewing geometry in the scan of Fig. 4.6. The curved lines represent radius contours of a slightly-tilted ring. The vertical lines represent the direction over which intensities are summed. Hence, the intensity value at a given radius is actually a weighted sum of contributions from external radii.

FIGURE 4.8. The bright ring's outer terminus in the contrast-enhanced discovery image, FDS 16368.19. Star trails and seven separate ring images are visible.

FIGURE 4.9. A sketch of the field of Fig. 4.8, identifying ring images and corresponding star trail segments.

deviation from a linear trajectory; spacecraft motion alone introduced nearly 500 pixels of smear to the frame (see Table 2.1). The many visible stars moved through the field as the camera wobbled, beginning at the upper left end of their kinked 200-pixel paths and ending at lower right. Star positions in the frame at any time may be estimated by integrating total light along a trail, and assuming that the star's light was laid down at a uniform rate. In this manner, we have managed to associate each of the seven visible ring images with sections of the kinked star trails.

In Fig. 4.9 we identify each of the ring images, along with its associated section on one of the star trails. Note that the ring terminus and star moved in opposite directions during the exposure. The six brightest ring images correspond to the nearly-vertical star trail segments. During these intervals, the ring did not shift appreciably in a direction perpendicular to itself, allowing time for its faint signature to be left on the vidicon. However, the ring did continue to shift radially by roughly 19 pixels (~ 180 km), so these views are of little use for new outer boundary determinations. The very faint first image also smeared, but in a direction 33° away from radial, so from it an outer boundary may be measured. Unfortunately, its large perpendicular smear component reduces the signal-to-noise ratio considerably. Figure 4.10 is a scan from this faint image, consisting of an average over nearly every pixel, in order to enhance the signal over the noise. Little believable structure, aside from the ring's outer boundary, is visible.

FIGURE 4.10. A radial profile of the bright ring's outer region, as measured from image #1 in FDS 16368.19. The RMS noise amplitude is also shown.

4.3 INTERPRETATIONS

To facilitate a more direct comparison of the radial profiles generated above, we reproject them all onto an identical radial scale and stack them vertically in Fig. 4.11. Here, the vertical scales are necessarily very different from profile to profile. Nevertheless, similarities between these completely independent scans are evident; the outer boundaries align quite closely, and several radial features recur in more than one scan.

The location of the bright Jovian ring's outer boundary, and its proximity to Adrastea, is of particular interest. Table 4.1 summarizes the measured properties of the scan boundaries, as well as various geometric uncertainties. Radii are given as the half-power point on the transition slope between bright ring and dark sky; this point remains relatively fixed when an image smears. Pointing errors must be expanded by a projection factor of $1/\sin\xi\sin\chi$, where χ is the angle on the image plane between the radial direction and the direction of pixel averaging, and ξ is the angle at the ring plane between the radius vector and the line of sight. Angle χ is based on true geometry in the first two images, and on smear alone in the second two.

The remarkable consistency between Table 4.1's independent measurements leads to a radius of 129130 ± 100 km for the ring. The table also lists the ring longitudes at which measurements were taken, defined in an inertial frame and also precessed to the epoch of FDS 20693.02. The precession rate used is that of a 129130 km

FIGURE 4.11. A comparison of the radial profiles from FDS 20693.02, 20692.53, 20630.52, and 16368.19. Orbital radii for Metis and Adrastea are also shown.

Table 4.1 Outer boundary of the bright Jovian ring

FDS	Precessed Longitude ^a (true) [°]	Phase Angle [°]	Radius ^b [km]	Uncertainty (camera + Voyager) ^d [km]	Width Measured ^c [km]	Width Predicted (resolution + smear) ^d [km]	Projection Factor
20693.02	277	173.9	129130	60 (30 + 30)	400	350 (220 + 130)	1.00
20692.53	251	174.4	129210	540 (10 + 30)	640	860 (27 + 36)	13.6
20630.52	126 (109)	19.0	129040	240 (25 + 30)	360	<240 (24 + <30)	4.45
16368.19	268 (272)	0.6	129130	80 (30 + 15)	160	<100 (21 + <30)	1.85

^aLongitudes in the PMEE frame (see Appendix A) are precessed to the epoch of FDS 20693.02. Unprecessed values are also given.

^bRadius location is the half-power point in the ring's outer boundary region.

^cWidth is the radial distance between intensities measured at 10% and 90% of the outer bright ring value.

^dIndividual components are given at the ring distance, but without projection factors.

ring, induced by Jupiter's gravitational moments J_2 and J_4 (from Aksnes, 1977). Since the scans cover a broad range of longitudes, we can infer that the ring is circular or nearly so, with eccentricity constrained to $< \sim 100/129130 = \sim 10^{-3}$.

A related question pertains to the actual abruptness of the outer boundary. In the table we also list the radial widths of the outer boundary regions, defined as the distance between intensities measured at 10% and 90% of the bright ring itself. This distance is the sum of three effects: image smear, resolution, and any genuine transition distance. We tabulate the radial dimensions of a resolution cell and the "residual" smear, meaning the smear which remains after the scan processing. This is merely an upper limit for the last two profiles, in which most of the smear present has already been removed. A systematic difference between the measured width and the sum of cell size plus smear would indicate a finite transition region. Except for the very badly-smearred second profile (from FDS 20692.53), the measurements are consistent with a radial transition distance of order 100 km. If real, this distance would differentiate Jupiter's ring from the very abruptly-bounded rings of Saturn and Uranus. However, the determination is quite marginal, and we are unable to conclusively rule out a more abrupt outer boundary for the bright Jovian ring.

The ring's radius, surprisingly, is ~ 150 km beyond the orbit of Adrastea. Indeed, Adrastea seems to lie in a region of decreasing intensity, between the ring terminus and an outer

"shoulder" region, located at 128750 ± 100 km. It may still play some role in defining the ring's outer limit, but it cannot be acting as a "classical" shepherd, such as in the model of Goldreich and Tremaine (1979), which seems to account for Saturn's narrow F ring. Instead, Adrastea's location seems crudely consistent with the model of Burns et al. (1984), in which the ring arises from dust which is raised off the satellites by micrometeoroid impacts and then evolves inward under drag forces. The 150-km radial offset from the outer boundary could arise from initial ejection velocities of ~ 35 m/s, so that some ejecta reaches out to 129130 km before drag forces take over; in the Burns model this is a quite plausible velocity, slightly larger than the ~ 10 m/s escape velocity. Adrastea, with an as-yet unconstrained eccentricity, may itself reach this radius near its apojove. Yet another possibility is that a population of smaller parent "moons" may simply extend ~ 150 km beyond the Adrastea orbit.

In addition to Adrastea, a set of strong orbital resonances lies in the vicinity of the ring's outer boundary. Burns et al. (1984b) note that Amalthea's 5:3 eccentricity and inclination resonances lie at 128900 km and 129420 km, near but on opposite sides of the ring boundary. However, neither of them seem to lie precisely atop it, and so their dynamical relevance to the ring remains uncertain.

The possible association of Metis with the bright annulus also needs to be considered. This feature is centered at

127600 \pm 100 km on the scans, fully 360 km inward from Metis' orbit. Like Adrastea, this satellite seems to be displaced outward from a notable feature, in a region of downward-sloping particle density. Its role may be in fact quite similar to that of Adrastea, in that its ejecta give rise to this feature; however the radial separation between the orbit and the peak intensity is not completely understood.

Both of the scans with sufficient signal and resolution (FDS 20693.02 and 20630.52) also show a third radial "hump" between the bright annulus near Metis and the outer shoulder near Adrastea. This feature is centered at 128250 \pm 100 km and is roughly 400 km wide. It looks quite similar to the bright annulus, though of slightly lower amplitude. One might argue, simply by analogy, that a third, as-yet undiscovered, satellite could engender this feature, at an orbit of \sim 128400 km. However, until a satisfactory theory explains how satellites give rise to these interior features, one should not extrapolate too far.

It is reassuring that we should observe the same radial features in both forward- and back-scattered light. Unfortunately, it is difficult to make direct comparison of the scans, because the in-plane backscattered views have a very different geometry. However, we can modify an out-of-plane profile $I(r)$ (e.g., Fig. 4.2), by letting each radial bin carry a contribution from external radii, as Fig. 4.7 suggests. This is accomplished via an integration:

$$I'(x) = \int_x^{\infty} I(r) \frac{r}{(r^2 - x^2)^{1/2}} dr \quad [4.1]$$

The new profile $I'(x)$ must then be rescaled to allow for the smear in the image it is mimicking. In Fig. 4.12 we present the profile from FDS 20693.02 (Fig. 4.2), reprocessed to show what we would have measured if its geometry and smear had been identical to FDS 20630.52 (Fig. 4.6). The overall I/F difference (a factor of 50!) is a result of the change in phase angle, and will be discussed in Chapter 6; here we simply compare the overall shapes of the figures.

This new curve does bear a crude resemblance to the profile of 20630.52. However, almost all trace of radial structure has vanished; the three humps only appear as subtle changes in slope. The fact that the humps are plainly visible in the backscattered image is now somewhat surprising, since features of the sort seen in forward-scatter should be invisible. Apparently, these features are narrower and/or relatively brighter in backscatter, as was also noted by Jewitt (1982). Unfortunately, it is not possible to go backward from this noisy ring-plane scan and uniquely determine the actual profile; this process is akin to differentiation, which enhances the noise and thereby obscures all structure. Baum et al. (1980) contend with similar difficulties in their inversion of the E Ring profile from an edge-on view.

The two lighting angles on the ring enhance very different

FIGURE 4.12. A hypothetical ring-plane scan from FDS 20693.02, processed to be identical to the scan from FDS 20630.52.

portions of the ring's particle size distribution, as is discussed in Appendix B. Smaller grains are highlighted in forward-scatter, while larger ones are emphasized in backscatter. Apparently, each bright feature is composed of a narrow core of larger particles, which is enveloped by the smaller, forward-scattering grains. The dynamical implications of this observations will be discussed in Chapter 6.

4.4 SUMMARY

The bright ring's outer boundary is centered at a radius of 129130 ± 100 km, and appears to have a radial width of 100 ± 100 km. Although the data do not rigorously exclude a perfectly abrupt boundary, they hint at a more gradual one. The eccentricity of the boundary is constrained to $< 10^{-3}$. The bright ring has an ill-defined inner boundary near 122000 km, where it gradually fades into the halo.

Three evenly-spaced brightness enhancements of ~10% amplitude are visible near the ring's outer boundary, centered on radii of 127600, 128250 and 128850 ± 100 km. Metis and Adrastea reside just outside the first and third of these and may give rise to them.

Other radial structure is seen in the scans on scales of a few hundred km, which is the effective resolution limit of the data. One can legitimately speculate that even finer structure is present; this possibility may be tested by images from the Galileo spacecraft near the decade's end.

CHAPTER 5

HALO MORPHOLOGY

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Examination of the WA, forward-scattered images (FDS 20691.27-.39, 20693.02) has indicated that the halo is crudely toroidal, and concentrated just inside the bright ring (see Chapter 3). Thus the halo, along with Saturn's G and E Rings (see Burns et al., 1984, and references therein), is one of the only rings known to have a substantial vertical extent. The implication is that very different dynamical processes are at work here, compared to the thinner, more substantial ring systems. In particular, electromagnetic forces are probably required to lift material out of the ring plane. These perturbations must act on a timescale shorter than the interparticle collisions, which damp material back to the ring plane. Since collision timescales are inversely proportional to optical depth, it is not coincidental that the Jovian halo and the G and E Rings are also among the most diffuse, optically thin rings known.

Several considerations make studies of the Jovian halo images very different from analogous studies for the bright ring. First, the halo is by its nature a diffuse system, unlikely to contain visible fine structure. Integrations of grain trajectories in this

region (Consolmagno, 1983; Schaffer and Burns, 1984) show an almost random character, so the orderly motions needed to give rise to fine structure seem to be excluded, if assumed charge-to-mass ratios are correct. As a result, image smearing is not nearly so important as in the case of the bright ring. This property makes our study of the halo somewhat easier, but it is more than compensated for by another--since the halo is vertically extended, each image pixel represents a line of sight which samples many regions above and below the ring plane, of a structure of uncertain form. Easily-interpreted measurements of the halo are therefore very difficult to acquire. In addition, the image background intensities cannot always be eliminated, particularly in the NA frames, because reference dark sky regions outside the halo are unavailable.

Ideally, we would like to see the Jovian halo in cross section, to understand how material is distributed both in radius and elevation. This distribution must be a consequence of the dynamics, and so is of great theoretical interest. Also, depending on the magnetic field's importance, the halo may be asymmetric about the planet's equatorial plane. Indeed, Jewitt and Danielson (1981) report a 300 km displacement between the apparent symmetry planes of the ring and disk. Though small, this may also be indicative of the magnetic field's role in halo particle dynamics.

5.2 "SLICING" THE HALO

The analysis of Chapter 3 demonstrated that the Jovian shadow boundary is very helpful for diagnosing the halo's three-dimensional structure, because it effectively makes a clean cut across the system. The ring and halo continue within the shadow of course but, since they are no longer illuminated and are optically thin, they may be ignored.

We have discovered a technique for producing a synthetic cross section of the halo, which involves using the shadow boundary as a "bologna-slicer" to isolate a thin halo sliver. Figure 5.1 is a sketch of the bright ring and halo near the shadow boundary, which is represented by a dashed grid. From this viewing angle, the ring is almost linear, so a shift of the figure parallel to the ring results in negligible change to the geometry everywhere except at the boundary (Fig. 5.2). Changes in scattering angle during the shift are also slight ($\sim 0.05^\circ$), so any photometric trend in the halo may be neglected. If we now subtract these two images the common portions vanish, so all that remains is a narrow slice of the ring and halo, of uniform thickness. Note that this procedure only works because the entire system is optically thin, so that all parts are equally visible.

Fig. 5.3 shows an enhanced version of FDS 20691.27, revealing the halo in a manner similar to Fig. 3.2, but with a grid system in radius (R) and elevation (Z) now overlaid. Jupiter's shadow may be regarded as an oblate cylindrical tunnel (see Fig. 5.1), with

FIGURE 5.1. A diagram of the ring and halo crossing the cylindrical shadow boundary, which is represented by a dashed grid.

FIGURE 5.2. The halo "slicing" technique. The ring/halo image is shifted to the left, which changes nothing except the shadow boundary. Subtraction then leaves behind a thin sliver of the halo, from which its variations with radius and elevation may be seen.

FIGURE 5.3. Image FDS 20691.27, enhanced to reveal the halo, and with a grid system on the shadow boundary surface overplotted. Radius contours are drawn in 20×10^3 km steps from 80 to 140×10^3 km; elevation contours are in 5×10^3 km steps from -15 to $+15 \times 10^3$ km. See text for a discussion of what these contours mean.

Voyager here looking down the tunnel toward the planet; this grid system is then simply painted on the tunnel wall. The lines represent the intersection of the tunnel wall with a cylindrical coordinate system in (R,Z) , centered on the Jovian axis. For example, a line of radius represents the locus of points which lie on the wall at a constant distance from Jupiter's rotation axis, i.e., the intersection of the tunnel wall with a cylinder centered on Jupiter's axis. Calculation of the shadow boundary (i.e., the tunnel wall) properly allows for Jupiter's oblateness, and also for the fact that the sun does not lie in the equatorial plane. Based on this scheme, each pixel outside the Jovian limb may be associated with a unique (R,Z) coordinate pair on the shadow surface.

Now we shift and subtract this image, pixel by pixel, as described above. The result (Fig. 5.4) reveals the unmistakable presence of a diffuse, vertically extended halo which runs roughly halfway down to the planet. It should be noted that this slicing technique makes no assumptions about the halo's vertical or radial structure. The method will work regardless of whether the system is a torus or a lens plus disk; by this exercise, the latter possibility is once again excluded.

One consequence of this processing is that, by differencing pixel intensities at nearby points, we implicitly remove any background light contribution. A background will be smooth and uniform, having at most a very slight gradient compared to that of the features we study, so most of it cancels when subtracted.

FIGURE 5.4. A "slice" of the halo from FDS 20691.27, enhanced in shades of gray to show the general vertical and radial distribution of material.

The resolution of this slice is limited by several problems. First, the images themselves are rather badly smeared (by 10-20 pixels; see Table 2.1), and this smear propagates through the shift-and-subtract operation. Second, the resultant slice has a finite thickness (~10 pixels in our processing) and is viewed obliquely (see Fig. 5.2); this decreases the resolution further, particularly in the radial direction. Overall, the halo/shadow boundary region only occupies an area of $\sim 200 \times 100$ pixels on the images, so we are not given much to work with at the outset. After the processing, the effective 10-20 pixel resolution cells are ~10% of the halo's overall scale.

It remains an inconvenience to be viewing this system from such an oblique angle in a distorted coordinate frame, as the grid system of Fig. 5.3 shows. It is now a straightforward geometric reprojection to compensate for this, and Fig. 5.5 contains the image presented within a rectangular coordinate frame. In Fig. 5.6 we plot approximate density contours from two of the images (FDS 20691.27, .35). The other two are so badly smeared initially that very little believable structure may be seen after this processing. The plots are in units of $\alpha \tilde{\omega}_0 P$, where linear extinction coefficient α is equivalent to optical depth per unit distance through the slice (see [2.15]).

Some important aspects of the halo may be seen in these contours. It seems to have a dense core region of $\sim 10^4$ km radial extent and ~ 2000 km vertical, though some of this core region is

FIGURE 5.5. The same halo slice as in Fig. 5.4, but here reprojected onto a rectangular grid. Labels on the horizontal (radius) and vertical (elevation) axes are in units of 10^3 km.

FIGURE 5.6. Halo intensity contours (in units of $\alpha \tilde{\omega}_0 P$) from FDS 20691.27 and 20691.35. Interference from the ring's far arm obscures part of the halo, as is shown by the dark band in each contour map. Also, the edge of the frame appears in the upper right corner of FDS 20691.35. The distinct slope of the central contours is an artifact of the processing.

confused by overlap from the slice of the bright ring. From here the density drops off quickly, and the halo can no longer be seen beyond $|Z| \gtrsim 8000$ km. The inner boundary is at $\sim 90 \times 10^3$ km. Some asymmetry about the planet's equatorial plane may be suggested; this will be discussed in the next section. Any difference between the absolute intensity scales in the two contour maps is the result of different color filters, and also different smears. The halo's color properties will be discussed in greater detail in Chapter 7.

Although this procedure gives a fairly unambiguous halo cross section, it is at the cost of some image signal-to-noise ratio. Each new pixel is the difference of two image pixels, so the subtraction simultaneously reduces the signal amplitude and enhances noise by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. The most distant reaches of the halo are so faint that, after the processing, nothing is left to be seen. Enhancement of the limb images, without any special processing, reveals the halo to extend out as far as $15\text{-}20 \times 10^3$ km above and below the ring plane, though with ever-diminishing intensity. By analogy, we cannot say conclusively that no halo material exists inward from $R = 90 \times 10^3$ km, only that any such material must be exceedingly faint.

5.3 VERTICAL ASYMMETRY

One might expect that the vertically-extended halo, if governed by Jupiter's magnetic field, should exhibit some asymmetry about the planet's equatorial plane. For example, very tiny

charged particles, if dominated by the magnetic forces, would be centered on the magnetic equator, just like electrons and protons; intermediate grains might be distributed around a plane somewhere between the two equators. Indeed, the integrations of Consolmagno (1983) and Schaffer and Burns (1984) both exhibit some asymmetry, in that magnetic longitudes exist where their trajectories are consistently shifted to one side of the equatorial plane or the other. The amount of this shift is proportional to the assumed charge-to-mass ratio, which in turn depends on assumed surface potential Φ , radius r and density ρ ; Schaffer and Burns find distances of ~ 200 km for $\Phi = -10$ V, $r = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, and $\rho = 2 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

Jewitt and Danielson (1981) reported the halo to be slightly asymmetric in the WA ansa view FDS 20693.02. In particular, they found it to be displaced southward (upward in the frame) by ~ 300 km, a distance corresponding to a mere 3 pixels in the image. We re-examine this possibility, studying a larger subset of the images.

Referring first back to the halo slices (Fig. 5.6), we note that the outer, most diffuse reaches of the halo may suggest some offset. However, extreme caution must be exercised here, because the far arms of the ring and halo are not quite parallel to the near arms in the images; hence they do not entirely cancel when shifted. This could easily introduce a tiny asymmetry into these noisy cross sections.

A simpler and more reliable approach to the question is based

upon vertical profiles across the ring and halo in the forward-scattered WA frames. Scan regions of this sort are depicted in Fig. 5.7, and a sample profile, from FDS 20691.27, is shown in Fig. 5.8. The scan regions are centered on a line which passes through both ring ansae, and is plotted as a function of projected distance normal to the ring plane. This distance is actually an average elevation; since our view is 2° from the equator, a range of elevations is sampled by each line of sight. Both ring arms are visible, as well as the superposition of two overlapping halo arms. In this approach, it is not possible to detect asymmetry in a single branch of the halo.

To the eye, Fig. 5.8 appears quite symmetric about $Z = 0$, indicating at the outset that the halo is not shifted markedly. To quantify this observation, we compare the scan to a mirror-reversed copy of itself, and determine the vertical offset between the two such that the halo cancels. This distance is 150 km here, and is even smaller (~ 50 km) in both FDS 20691.31 and the ansa frame, where the asymmetry was first reported. This is the rough order of the accuracy to which the scans can be measured, since a single pixel corresponds to ~ 100 km. It is also the order of the visible asymmetry expected simply from the fact that the system is viewed from a finite distance. Thus, our measurements are consistent with a halo that is perfectly symmetric about the ring plane; we cannot confirm the 300 km offset previously reported.

Before making the profiles, care must be taken to subtract

FIGURE 5.7. The geometry of scans which constrain the halo's asymmetry. If the ring and halo are symmetric about the equatorial plane, then intensity profiles with elevation Z (through the regions shown) should also be symmetric.

FIGURE 5.8. A sample profile from FDS 20691.27, using the geometry shown in Fig. 5.7 and described in the text. The halo light, outside the two peaks from the ring arms, is asymmetric about $Z = 0$ by less than 150 km.

out a background ramp, which could introduce some asymmetry of its own. This is accomplished, as usual, by fitting a quadratic of line and sample to the dark regions of the images. These regions include dark sky areas far from the ring and halo, and also regions on the dark side of the planet. Without this correction, an asymmetry could indeed be found; this may have been the origin of Jewitt and Danielson's misinterpretation. Indeed, as will be shown in Chapter 8, the WA ansa image data which they used probably had a very strong background gradient.

So far, we have omitted mention of the other WA forward-scattered views, FDS 20691.35 and .39. These do in fact show a huge (~600 km) asymmetry in the halo, though it is not compatible with a simple vertical shift. However, the frames also show a far ring arm substantially brighter than the near arm. This magnitude of difference does not seem to be reasonable, particularly in the context of other image measurements. We note that, in these frames, the ring occupies only a rather small number of pixels near the lower right corner. Calibration near the corners of Voyager images is always rather variable and uncertain, so we believe that asymmetry in this frame can be more easily explained by flaws in the image data.

5.4 INTERPRETATIONS

Perhaps the halo's biggest puzzle is its inner boundary. Here the halo ceases to exist, and yet there is no apparent sink

for the material. It may be that the system is simply in a delicate balance, in which the timescale for destruction of the grains (by sputtering and erosion) is very close to the timescale for orbital decay, presumably under plasma drag. This balance may be simply a numerical coincidence. However, Schaffer and Burns (1984) have recently put forward a more promising explanation. They have located a very strong Lorentz resonance at 1.3-1.4 R_J ($93-100 \times 10^3$ km), where a grain's orbital period is commensurate with one of the vertical forcing periods of the magnetic field. In this plausible scenario, material in the halo continues to evolve inward until it reaches the resonant orbit, where it is rapidly dispersed in elevation and thus can no longer be seen.

The halo's symmetry about the ring plane suggests that its constituent particles may not be as small as had been previously thought. Although the magnetic field perturbs the halo grains out of the ring plane, gravity dominates their motion. The particles may follow essentially Keplerian trajectories, such that it is only the long-term sum of magnetic field deflections which lifts them to higher elevations.

The ratio of the primary magnetic to gravitational forces on a particle may be written (cf. Burns et al., 1984, eq. [4a]).

$$\frac{F_M}{F_G} = \frac{qB(\Omega - \omega)}{mc\Omega^2} \quad [5.1]$$

Here $q = \Phi r$ is the particle's charge, where Φ is its surface potential; $m = (4/3)\pi r^3 \rho$ is its mass, Ω is its orbital frequency, ω is the planet's rotation frequency, B is the local magnetic field, and c is the speed of light. For Jupiter, this becomes

$$\frac{F_M}{F_G} = 0.11 \left(\frac{r}{\mu\text{m}}\right)^{-2} \left(\frac{\Phi}{-10\text{V}}\right) \left(\frac{R}{10^5 \text{ km}}\right)^{-3} \left(\frac{\omega(\Omega - \omega)}{\Omega^2}\right) \quad [5.2]$$

where R is the grain's orbital radius. The last term has a nearly constant value of 0.24 in the Jovian halo. For particles with $\Phi = -10\text{V}$, the ratio is unity at $r = 0.2 \mu\text{m}$; grains of this size or smaller may be excluded from the halo, because they would not be symmetric about the ring plane. However, the grain surface potential Φ is not well-constrained, so one should not regard this as an absolutely rigid limit.

It should be noted that the outer contours of Fig. 5.6 are evenly-spaced in elevation. Since the contour lines themselves differ by factors of two in $\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0 P$, this indicates an exponential decay with Z . The corresponding scale height, measured from the contours, is roughly 3000 km at $R = 110,000$ km. Any successful theory of halo dynamics will have to account for this property. The analogous behavior of density in an isothermal atmosphere is probably unrelated, because halo particles collide too infrequently (see below).

To account for the halo's vertical extent, magnetic perturbations must act more rapidly than flattening, which takes place on

the order of the collision timescale T_C . This is approximately

$$T_C = \frac{P}{2\tau} \quad [5.3]$$

(cf. Burns et al., 1984, eq. [15]), where P is the grain's orbital period. Here normal optical depth τ represents the rough probability of a collision during each pass through the ring plane, and those passages occur twice during each orbital period. Jewitt (1982) quotes $\tau \lesssim 5 \times 10^{-6}$ for the halo (cf. Chapter 7), which suggests $T_C \gtrsim 100$ yr. For comparison, the vertical deflection timescale T_Z may be approximated by

$$T_Z = \frac{2\pi}{(\Omega - \omega)} \frac{F_G}{F_M \sin\gamma}, \quad [5.4]$$

where $\gamma \cong 10^\circ$ is the tilt angle of the magnetic field with respect to the rotation axis. The first factor is the synodic period between the orbit and the magnetic field, which is on the order of 10 hours in the halo. The second term is the inverse ratio of the vertical perturbation force to gravity, and may be evaluated from [5.2]. For F_M/F_G as small as 10^{-4} , T_Z will still be shorter than T_C and the halo will not flatten. Hence quite tiny surface potentials are adequate to thicken the halo.

Burns et al. (1984) derive an expression for the maximum vertical amplitude reached by an orbiting grain, induced by

perturbations from an inclined magnetic dipole:

$$Z_{\max} = \frac{q B \sin \gamma R}{mc\omega} \left(\frac{\Omega - \omega}{2\Omega - \omega} \right) \quad [5.5]$$

(their eq. [19]). For Jupiter's magnetic field this reduces to

$$Z_{\max} = 2000 \left(\frac{r}{\mu\text{m}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{\Phi}{-10\text{V}} \right) \left(\frac{R}{10^5 \text{ km}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{\Omega - \omega}{2\Omega - \omega} \right) \quad [5.6]$$

The last term varies from 0.25 to 0.40 for the Jovian halo. According to this expression, displacements of a few $\times 10^3$ km are to be expected, for surface potentials near -10V and radii near 1 μm . Higher-order magnetic field components, which are important close to Jupiter but have been neglected in this discussion, will distribute material even further (cf. Schaffer and Burns, 1984).

5.5 SUMMARY

The halo appears to have a very dense central core, as well as diffuse outer regions extending as far as $\sim 15 \times 10^3$ km out of the ring plane. Its inner boundary is near 90×10^3 km in orbital radius, roughly halfway between the ring and the Jovian cloudtops. Apparently, it is almost perfectly symmetric about the ring plane.

Both the halo's symmetry and its vertical extent may be understood in terms of constituent grains which are weakly perturbed by the magnetic field. Such grains must be larger than

~0.2 μm in radius; further constraints on the halo particle sizes will be found in Chapter 7.

The halo's inner boundary is more mysterious, but the nearby Lorentz resonance seems to be a likely cause. The equations [5.5] and [5.6] do not apply to the resonant situation, and so halo material in this region may be lifted to much greater elevations. In the end, these grains may leave the system, perhaps by entering Jupiter's clouds, or may simply disperse too far to be seen any longer.

CHAPTER 6

PROPERTIES OF THE BRIGHT RING PARTICLES

6.1 INTRODUCTION

As we have pointed out previously, the ring is known to scatter substantially more light into high phase angles than into small ones. Owen et al. (1979) report this ratio to be at least 20:1, while we note a factor of 50 in §4.3. The forward-scattered images alone contain a noticeable photometric trend, as is illustrated by contrast enhancement of FDS 20691.27 in Fig. 6.1. By measuring the intensity of light scattered into various phase angles, we wish to infer the sizes and properties of the Jovian ring particles. Unfortunately, our limited image catalog samples only a very few angles (summarized in Table 1.1 and Fig. 1.2), so a complete description will not be possible.

Jewitt and Danielson (1981), using a subset of the images that cover scattering angle $\theta \sim 4\text{-}6^\circ$, measured the ring's relative phase function in this range. Their data were consistent with a ring composed entirely of ice spheres (refractive index $m = 1.33 - 0.0i$) of radius $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$. It is obviously unphysical to assume that the ring contains only a single grain size, but this number has been widely interpreted as a "typical" radius. Grün et al. (1980) and Tyler et al. (1981) fit broader distributions to the

FIGURE 6.1. A contrast-enhanced version of FDS 20691.27, showing that the main ring brightens significantly between scattering angles of 4.6° and 3.8° . Contours of scattering angle are overplotted.

same data; nevertheless, their models still contain a preponderance of $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ particles, and so in practical terms are not very different from Jewitt and Danielson's monodispersed description. It should be noted, however, that these data fall into the diffraction lobe of $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ grains, so the micron size range was preselected before any measurements were taken. Therefore the data cannot be interpreted as evidence for a dearth of particles either much larger or much smaller than a few microns.

The other half of the Jovian ring images, those showing the ring in backscatter, provide a very different set of constraints on ring particle sizes and properties. This lighting angle emphasizes the macroscopic bodies in the ring ($r \gg \lambda$), which show fully-lit faces at this viewing angle, but only narrow crescents in the forward-scatter frames. In particular, these images allow the best estimates of the ring's optical depth, since macroscopic bodies backscatter light in direct proportion to their cross-sectional areas. However, the proportionality constant (geometric albedo k) must be assumed.

Only two previous "representative value" measurements of the ring's backscatter intensity have been published, by Owen et al. (1979) and Jewitt and Danielson (1981). The latter investigators measure the intensity from FDS 16368.19 and use [2.14] to determine $\tau = 3 \times 10^{-5}$. They assume $k \equiv \tilde{\omega}_0 P/4 = 0.04$, a representative value for Amalthea. They do not present the actual intensity measurement, or describe how the factor $1/\mu$ is determined for this

in-plane view (where it approaches infinity). Owen et al. report the ring to be $\sim 3 \times 10^{-5}$ of Jupiter's mean brightness at zero phase, based on the "brightest segment" of the ring in FDS 20612.27/.31. It is unclear whether this number includes a subtraction of Jovian scattered light, or corrections for oblique viewing geometry and smear. Nevertheless, Tyler et al. (1981) assume it to be a corrected intensity ratio, and infer $\tau = 4.5 \times 10^{-5}$. They use the same value for k , but appear to have an incorrect factor of π in their equations.

6.2 FORWARD-SCATTER PHOTOMETRY

The foremost difficulty in any photometry of the Jovian ring system is that each pixel in an image represents the intensity from a line of sight through both the ring and the halo. Contributions from each component must somehow be separated before reliable conclusions may be drawn. Uncertainties in the halo/disk contribution are apparently the principal source of the sizable error bars in Jewitt and Danielson's (1981) measurements, though image smear may also play a role. Here we repeat and expand upon their forward-scattering measurements. We carefully model the halo contribution and image smear, and also incorporate more images, including some through color filters and at previously unexamined scattering angles.

Our first step is to take scans across the bright ring in each of the NA mosaic images (FDS 20692.37-.53), in order to obtain

rough plots of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ versus radius at constant scattering angle. An example of one of these is shown in Fig. 6.2, from a region of FDS 20692.53 (cf. Figs. 4.3 and 4.4). The halo contribution is unambiguous in the right and left regions, which we know are beyond the bright ring's limits. For our purposes here, it is of no matter that an inappropriate dark current might contribute (or remove) a significant fraction of this light. We believe the halo to be a diffuse, optically thin cloud, vertically extended, and concentrated just inside the ring's inner edge. Integrated along lines of sight just 2° away from parallel to the ring plane, we expect its scan contribution to be smooth, with a broad peak near the ring's inner edge. This is represented by the dashed curve in the figure. The remaining intensity should be a smeared version of the bright ring profiles already shown (Fig. 4.2). From the area of this remaining region, a mean $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ for the ring may be established.

We model the halo contribution empirically with a six-parameter function:

$$h(R) = (A + BR) e^{-[(C + DR + ER^2)^F]} \quad [6.1]$$

For $B = 0$ and $F = 1$ this is a simple Gaussian; parameter B allows the curve to be somewhat asymmetric, and F allows for some control over how quickly the curve's exponential tails drop to zero. Other empirical descriptions were tried, but this one was found to be

FIGURE 6.2. A radial profile of the bright ring and halo, measured at constant scattering angle, from FDS 20692.57. The shaded region is a fit to the halo component.

most successful, fitting the halo profile outside the ring with mean residuals of a few percent or less.

Furthermore, something is known of the form of the remaining bright ring contribution. Its overall shape should be a smeared, shifted, rescaled version of the ring's known radial profile (Fig. 4.2). The smear can be represented by a single parameter D_{sm} , which describes the radial distance over which the smearing occurred. This assumes it to be linear, equivalent to convolving the ring profile with a "boxcar" function of unit area and width D_{sm} . It is also multiplied by some factor Q , which represents the ratio of the ring's phase function at this scattering angle to that at the angle where the reference profile is measured. This ratio is assumed to be constant across the ring's radial width, so we neglect the possibility that particle sizes may vary with radius. The profile may also have to be translated by a distance D_{tr} to account for errors in the precise camera pointing. These three ring parameters plus six halo parameters may then be fit to any measured profile, although only the amplification factor Q is of interest for this study. The dashed curve in Fig. 6.2 is $h(R)$ from our best nine-parameter fit to the scan shown.

One further inconvenience must be considered. We have assumed above that our reference profile (Fig. 4.2) has no halo contribution at all. At first this seems reasonable, for we believe that the halo is interior to the ring, and so not present at the *ansa* where this scan was taken. However, some small halo

contribution must still leak through, as is demonstrated by the fact that the profile does not drop to zero at its inner edge. We model this contribution as a straight line (shown dashed in Fig. 4.2), which should be constant, independent of scattering angle. In our first pass through the problem, the two additional parameters needed to describe this term were therefore included. Afterward they were averaged over all the fits, and then left fixed as shown for the second pass. Since these parameters only affect a small portion of the bright ring pixels, their precise values are not critical.

Finally, a plot of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ versus scattering angle, measured from nearly all of the clear forward-scattered images, is given in Fig. 6.3. Only FDS 20692.57 and 20693.01 are excluded, the former because it is too badly smeared and the latter because it did not capture the bright ring at all. The vertical axis variable $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ is defined as the value of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ which we would have measured if the ring had been homogenized, to show a uniform intensity between 122,000 and 129,000 km, with nothing inside or outside. So defined, the ring's maximum peak in Fig. 4.2 is 50% brighter than the mean value.

The consistency between neighboring scans on the same image (designated by connected points in the figure) suggests at the outset that our scan modelling is reasonable. Fit residuals are typically ~3% within the ring's limits and better than 1% on the halo alone, here expressed as fractions of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$. Hence, the

FIGURE 6.3. Bright ring forward-scattered photometry through the clear filter, based on five NA images (FDS 2069237-.53) and one WA image (FDS 20693.02). Measurements from the near and far ring arms are distinguished, and $\sim 10\%$ asymmetry is seen for $\theta \geq 5^\circ$. The open and closed symbols distinguish WA and NA measurements.

intrinsic errors in our measurements are of this order. Error bars plotted in Fig. 6.3 correspond to the RMS residual within the ring's boundaries.

It should be noted that Fig. 6.3 is flatter by nearly a factor of two than the phase curve of Jewitt and Danielson (1981). Although they do not describe their measurement procedure, it is possible that the discrepancy lies in their inadequate modelling of the halo's light contribution. Near the ring, the halo contributes a large fraction of the light and also exhibits a steep intensity gradient, so it is difficult to know what should be the "typical" halo intensity to subtract from a ring measurement. Also, since they believed that a disk was present, they could only measure halo light outward from the bright ring; their extrapolated estimates of its contribution within the ring are therefore even more uncertain. Note in Fig. 6.2 the large difference (roughly a factor of two) between halo intensities on opposite sides of the ring. Finally, smear can easily reduce the ring intensity by a factor of two, and must be modelled accurately.

Additional orange and violet photometry at an extended range of scattering angles ($\theta \sim 3-4^\circ$) is available from FDS 20691.27-.39. Unfortunately, a combination of low resolution, considerable smear and an oblique view severely degrades these images. Overall, the ring images are blurred to more than twice their original width; as a result, the above technique no longer converges to physically-reasonable fits. For example, in some

scans the halo model [6.1] alone can be fit to the data, implying $Q = 0$. To compensate for this, we fit $h(R)$ only to points outside the bright ring, and determine Q from the remaining area. We must also more severely constrain the halo model, by fixing parameter F to unity throughout. The result is a set of measurements which are reasonably self-consistent and show believable slopes, but which may be inaccurate in absolute scale by $\sim 50\%$. They are shown in Fig. 6.4.

6.3 NEAR/FAR ARM ASYMMETRY

Like our predecessors, we note that the ring's far (upper) arm appears to be consistently brighter than its near (lower) arm (see Fig. 1.7). The difference is more than 10% near the ansa (larger scattering angles in Fig. 6.3) and decreases to zero in about 45° of longitude on both ring arms.

The explanation proffered by Jewitt and Danielson is that this is additional light scattered by halo material between the ring and the spacecraft. However, if a smooth halo brightens the ring, it will brighten the neighboring off-ring regions as well, and so should have been accounted for in our modelling. In addition, there is no obvious reason why the halo should brighten one ring arm more than the other. For every halo point contributing light in front of the far arm, there exists a corresponding halo point behind the near arm, contributing a similar amount. Since both components are optically thin, it makes no difference

FIGURE 6.4. Bright ring forward-scattered photometry through the orange and violet filters. For comparison, the clear measurements are designated by the dashed line. Absolute calibration of these measurements may be in error by $\sim 50\%$. The sizable near/far arm discrepancy in FDS 20691.35/.39 is probably the result of variable vidicon response near the image corner.

which is in front. Only a halo which is both markedly asymmetric and not smooth could cause this effect, and we have no reason to believe that the halo manifests either trait.

Another possibility is that the additional far arm brightness arises from light reflected off the Jovian disk. After all, at the ring orbit in front of Jupiter, the flux of light reflected from the planet is ~18% that from the sun in the visible range (Simonelli, private communication, 1984). However, this light would have to be backscattered from Jupiter to Voyager, and so it would be reduced by the factor of at least 20 between large and small phase angles. Thus Jupiter-shine cannot contribute even 1% of the solar forward-scattered light, whereas a 10% enhancement is seen. Additionally, such light would tend to increase from the ansa to the limb, as ring particles see larger fractions of the lit disk, whereas a steady decrease in the extra brightness is observed.

The cause of this asymmetry is therefore mysterious. It may be analogous to brightness variations which have been reported in Saturn's vast but faint E Ring from groundbased observations (Lamy and Maun, 1981; Dollfus and Brunier, 1982), as well as from results of Voyager's low-energy charged particle experiment (Carbary et al., 1983). However, these variations have not been seen by all observers (Baum et al., 1981; Larson et al., 1981), and so remain somewhat controversial. Since noise and scattered light are large in all E Ring observations, and these can masquerade as

variable structure, reports of this sort should be approached with some skepticism.

One possibility worth considering is that a recent impact into a larger Jovian ring body might have released new material, which would then take some time to spread in longitude. Brightening 45° of the ring by 10% requires an extra $\sim 1\%$ of the total ring cross section in micron-sized grains. Material which is ejected from a ring moon will have typical velocities $\sim 10\text{--}100$ m/s (see Burns et al., 1984, Fig. 19) and so will span a 45° range of longitude in 6–60 days. If this were a "typical" impact event, then the ring's entire complement of micron-sized grains could be replaced in less than (and possibly much less than) 20 years. Estimates of grain removal timescales (Burns et al., 1984) are all much longer than this, so the scenario seems unlikely. If the excess brightness was caused by a recent impact, then our detection of it was an exceedingly improbable occurrence.

Perhaps we are seeing a quadrant asymmetry similar to that documented for Saturn's A ring (Thompson et al., 1981; also Cuzzi et al., 1984 and references therein). The same effect is seen in the color measurements (Fig. 6.4): brighter far arms in FDS 20691.35/.39, and brighter near arms in FDS 20691.27/.31, at the opposite limb. However, scaling uncertainties, particularly in 20691.35/.39 (see §5.3), make it unclear whether the trends in these particular images are real. A view of the other ansa would resolve the question, but, sadly, does not exist. Nevertheless, for the range of orbital longitudes observed, both the direction

and the amplitude (10% versus 15% maximum at Saturn) of the trends are quite comparable.

This phenomenon has not been entirely explained for the A ring; it is widely attributed to (though not totally explained by) mutual shadowing of ring particles in the density "wakes" produced by larger ring members (see Cuzzi et al., 1984). However, such an explanation could not work in Jupiter's diaphanous ring system, where interparticle shadowing is out of the question.

An alternate explanation for the quadrant asymmetry involves elongated particles locked preferentially into a specific orientation, and so showing a variable cross section when viewed from different angles (Ferrín, 1974). This is thought to be untenable at Saturn where collisions reorient particles regularly (Cuzzi et al., 1984).

However, at Jupiter collisions are infrequent, so this explanation deserves closer scrutiny. Tidal forces are incapable of locking the rotation of the microscopic visible grains, but the magnetic field may have the ability to orient them, much as it does for interstellar dust. The resultant asymmetry might relate to viewing quadrant or magnetic longitude, or possibly both. At the time of this imaging sequence, the Jovian magnetic equator was elevated farthest north at a point 13° in longitude from the ansa on the ring's near arm; this point falls well within the ansa region, near $\theta = 6^\circ$ on Fig. 6.3. Hence, our data cannot distinguish between an asymmetry centered either on this longitude or on the apparent ansa.

6.4 INTERPRETATIONS OF FORWARD-SCATTER

It is apparent that the ring brightens considerably, by at least a factor of two, between scattering angles θ of 6 and 4°. This strongly suggests the diffraction of light by particles with size parameters $X \approx \pi/\theta \approx 30$ (see Appendix B). This corresponds to particles of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ radius for the 0.50 μm center wavelength of the clear filters. Appendix B contains a brief description of light scattering properties for particles of various sizes, and our methods for calculating them.

The diffraction lobe is particularly useful for constraining particle sizes, because in this regime scattering properties are nearly independent of refractive index m . Only a particle's shape and size determine how electromagnetic waves diffract about its surface. The exception is nearly lossless grains (imaginary component of m small, as in, say, pure ice particles), for which a portion of the wave will also refract through the particle; its interference with the diffracted wave will alter the scattering pattern. However, for the rocky or carbonaceous grains inferred from groundbased spectrophotometry (Smith and Reitsema, 1980; Neugebauer et al., 1981; see also Burns et al., 1984), lossless grains may be reasonably excluded from consideration. Photometric functions calculated in this section are all based on $m = 1.5 - 0.01i$, but are almost unaltered for $\text{Re}(m) \gtrsim 1.3$ and $-\text{Im}(m) \gtrsim 0.003$ (cf. Tyler et al., 1981).

We first compare the measured ring properties with phase functions of single particle sizes (Fig. 6.5), as was done by Jewitt and Danielson (1981). Although the curves corresponding to $X = 15-20$ match crudely, none of them fit to within the observational errors. Note particularly that all these curves are concave downward, whereas the measured curves in Fig. 6.3 and 6.4 bend distinctly upward. A broader, more complex size distribution is called for.

It should be noted that the curves measured in orange ($\lambda = 0.614 \mu\text{m}$) and in violet ($\lambda = 0.431 \mu\text{m}$) light are of nearly constant ratio (Fig. 6.4). This is also inconsistent with a single particle size; for a given grain radius, the corresponding X is smaller in the orange than in the violet by a factor of 1.5, which should lead to a very different phase function slope. This is certainly not observed.

Indeed, the constant orange-to-violet ratio is suggestive of a very different size distribution: a power law. Such a distribution is described by

$$n(r) = C r^{-p} \quad [6.2]$$

where $n(r)dr$ is the number of particles per unit ring area in the size range from r to $r+dr$ (see §2.5) and constant p is the spectral index. Power-law size distributions have the unique property that they appear similar regardless of the scale at which they are

FIGURE 6.5. The data of Fig. 6.3 is compared to single-particle phase functions, with size parameter X . All phase functions are normalized to the same value at $\theta = 6^\circ$.

measured; in effect there does not exist a "typical" particle size. Since the wavelength of light imposes the "yardstick" by which particles are measured, phase functions of a power law size distribution are wavelength-independent in many circumstances. Properties of these distributions are discussed in greater detail in Appendix B.

In Fig. 6.6 we present phase functions calculated for power laws with a range of different indices p . Larger indices correspond to a preponderance of small particles, which have a nearly isotropic scattering pattern, and therefore their phase functions are flat; for smaller indices, large particles are more common and so steeper phase functions result. The data of Fig. 6.3 fit a power law with $p = 2.5 \pm 0.5$ quite well.

Another characteristic of a power law size distribution is that the intensity measured is proportional to λ^{3-p} (see Appendix B, equation B.11). Since diffraction dominates, this ratio has nothing to do with the actual color of the grain material. For $p = 2.5$, we would expect a ratio of ~ 1.19 between the Voyager orange and violet filters. Initially this compares unfavorably to the measured ratio of 1.64 ± 0.11 . However, new calibration factors, determined by Buratti (private communication, 1984) to bring Voyager-based photometry into agreement with Earth-based measurements, reduce this ratio by 20% to 1.32 ± 0.10 . This corresponds to $p = 2.2 \pm 0.2$.

Our arrival at nearly the same range of spectral index by two

FIGURE 6.6. The data of Fig. 6.3 is compared to phase functions of power laws, with spectral index p . All phase functions are normalized to the same value at $\theta = 6^\circ$.

independent methods strongly suggests that this power law correctly describes the ring. Other size distributions could be invented which fit the data equally well, but they would be necessarily ad hoc in nature. A power law has the advantage of simplicity, with only one free parameter to be determined. Power laws are also found elsewhere in nature. The particles of Saturn's rings between radii of ~ 1 cm and ~ 5 m are fitted by a power law with $p = 3.1 \pm 0.3$ (Marouf et al., 1983; see also Cuzzi et al., 1984), while high-velocity impact ejecta are described by $p \approx 3.4$ (Grün et al., 1980). Dohnanyi (1972) finds power-law fits to the size distributions of asteroids ($p \approx 3.5$), comets ($p \approx 3.1$), zodiacal light particles ($p < 2$) and meteoroids entering the Earth's atmosphere ($p \approx 5.0$).

No power law may continue without limit to both large and small radii, for it would then represent an infinity of particles. We must therefore ask what size range contributes most to the scattered intensities. Figure 6.7 shows the relative contribution to the scattered light between 4° and 6° , from particle sizes in equal log-intervals. The curves are presented for three spectral indices, and are normalized to unity when integrated over $d\log(X)$. We see that most of the light is scattered by particles from $X \approx 4$ to 200, or $r \approx 0.3$ to $16 \mu\text{m}$. We claim that this is the minimum size range over which our size distribution applies; it may, of course, extend much further in either direction. However, the figure shows that the $p = 2$ case is exceptional, for here

FIGURE 6.7. The fractional contribution from particles in a power-law size distribution (index p) to the scattered intensity between $\theta = 4^\circ$ and 6° . This function is normalized such that its integral by $d(\log X)$ equals one.

larger particles seem to play ever-greater roles, with the total cross-sectional area proportional to the upper cutoff.

Assuming now that this size distribution is close to the truth, we may use the absolute calibration of our measurements to determine the actual number density of ring particles within a given size range. In effect, we seek the constant factor C in [6.2]. This number depends rather strongly on the precise value of p : for $p = 2.0$, $C = 0.98 \pm 0.13 \text{ cm}^{-2}$; for $p = 2.5$, $C = 1.71 \pm 0.10 \text{ cm}^{-2}$; for $p = 3.0$, $C = 2.12 \pm 0.07 \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The units in these constants are based on radii r expressed in microns. In general, they are weakly dependent on the assumed upper size cutoff; for $p = 2$ the dependence is stronger.

Finally, this complete description of $n(r)$ allows us to predict a normal optical depth for the ring in micron-sized grains. Since $n(r)$ is a power-law, this number depends strongly on the upper cutoff chosen. Figure 6.8 is the total optical depth $\tau(r)$ for particles up to radius r , at wavelength $\lambda = 0.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Particles smaller than $X \approx 1$ do not interact significantly with light, so the lower cutoff is unimportant. The calculated curves are essentially independent of refractive index. We find that for grains up to $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in radius, optical depths are $1\text{-}6 \times 10^{-6}$, depending strongly on the precise p .

If the distribution extends to still larger particles, we enter the "geometric optics" limit (see Appendix B), where

$$\tau(r) = \int_{r_{\min}}^r 2\pi r^2 \cdot n(r) dr \quad [6.3]$$

FIGURE 6.8. Optical depth from a power-law size distribution (index p) as a function of upper size cutoff r .

For the power law of [6.2], this becomes

$$\tau(r) = \frac{2\pi C}{3-p} r^{3-p} \quad [6.4a]$$

or, for $p = 3$,

$$\tau(r) = 2\pi C \log \left(\frac{r}{r_{\min}} \right) . \quad [6.4b]$$

Using [6.4], optical depths may be extrapolated to any size range, under the assumption that the power-law still applies.

The measured power-law index p probably bears some relation to the origin and dynamics of the bright ring's grains. According to the ideas summarized in §1.5, the tiny grains probably originate as impact ejecta off of larger bodies in the ring. Hence they should be produced with the characteristic power-law index $p = 3.4$ for collisional ejecta (Grün et al., 1980). However, in their discussion of theoretical ring profiles, Burns et al. (1984) note that smaller grains evolve more rapidly than large, and that this tends to flatten a size distribution. Both plasma drag and Poynting-Robertson drag forces are proportional to grain area ($\propto r^2$), so their accelerations are proportional to r^{-1} and their timescales are proportional to r . Burns et al. predict that the nonuniformity of evolution rates should decrease p overall by exactly 1, to $p = 2.4$. This theoretically-derived value is in remarkable agreement with the measured power-law index.

6.5 BACKSCATTER PHOTOMETRY

Photometry from the backscatter images is not an entirely straightforward process. Low signal-to-noise ratio, polluting light from Jupiter, extensive smear and confusing viewing geometry all contribute to the difficulties. Nevertheless, the ring's mean brightness, in terms of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$, may be extracted from an image once the geometry is understood.

For ring plane views, we measure an I/F profile across the ring as a function of projected distance normal to the plane, averaging over a wide path to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. The scan geometry is sketched in Fig. 6.9a, and a corresponding profile (from FDS 20630.24) is shown in Fig. 6.10. The 700 km thickness of the ring in this scan is due almost exclusively to smear. We then subtract the mean of the surrounding off-ring regions to eliminate background light; this is primarily Jupiter-shine scattered into the camera, but may include halo and dark current contributions as well. Note that the remaining area A under a curve like Fig. 6.10 is smear-independent; if the ring had smeared half as much, it would show twice the given mean intensity. Hence A , in units of $I/F \cdot \text{km}$, may be calculated unambiguously. We are more interested in the \bar{I}/F which we would have measured from a view normal to the ring plane. To get this, we divide A by the total distance d across the ring for this in-plane line of sight (Fig. 6.9b). Finally, our determination of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ is simply $4\bar{I}/F$ (by [2.14]), since the geometric projection factor μ has already been incorporated into the distance ratio.

FIGURE 6.9. Geometry of smeared ring plane views.
 (a) The region of averaging for two scans across the ring. The vertical thickness in these scans is due almost entirely to smear.
 (b) The corresponding ring area contributing to each scan, including the line-of-sight distances d across the ring. The other half of these distances is in the lower quadrant, not shown. Note that scan #2 does not sample all ring radii.

FIGURE 6.10. A vertical profile of the smeared, edge-on ring, from FDS 20630.24. The geometry is comparable to scan #1 in Fig. 6.9.

To calculate the distance d , we assume the ring to be bounded between $R = 122,000$ and $129,000$ km. Thus, as before, our numbers actually apply to a uniform ring which scatters the same amount of light as that seen. This may bias the measurements, since the scan areas, once projected onto the ring plane, do not sample all radii between $122,000$ and $129,000$ km equally (see Fig. 6.9b). This problem is most severe near the ring terminus; measurements from FDS 16368.19, 20630.48 and 20630.52 are especially open to this systematic error.

To counter some of this error, we take scans with identical geometry whenever possible. For example, the color images FDS 20630.36/.40/.44 capture an almost-identical field, so it is not difficult to select the same measurement region in each. Thus, our color measurements should be quite self-consistent, even if some small overall error persists.

The measurement procedure for views from out of the ring plane (e.g., FDS 20612.27, .31) is qualitatively similar, in that we assume the area under an I/F scan across the ring to be smear-invariant. However, here we plot the profile as a function of true ring radius, and divide the measured area by the 7000 km assumed range. The factor of 4μ then converts from \bar{I}/F to $\tau\omega_0P$.

Figure 6.11 contains all the backscattered measurements as a function of phase angle, including several through Voyager's color filters. This represents the entire suite of information currently available on the ring's backscattering characteristics.

FIGURE 6.11. Bright ring backscatter photometry, including variations with phase angle and color. Included are the FDS counts and colors of the images from which the measurements were taken.

6.6 INTERPRETATIONS OF BACKSCATTER

Several aspects of the backscatter measurements in Fig. 6.11 require comment. First, we find the ring to be fainter in backscatter than forward-scatter by about a factor of 60. This value is three times larger than Owen et al.'s (1979) determination. Second, color measurements at $\alpha = 18^\circ$ show the ring to be distinctly red, with an orange-to-violet ratio of nearly two. Third, the ring brightens considerably between $\alpha = 18^\circ$ and 2.5° . We discount the anomalously low intensity measurements from FDS 16368.19 (the discovery image) at 0.5° , because of the unusual cross-ansa viewing geometry mentioned previously, as well as the uncertain calibration of such a lengthy exposure.

Several of the ring's backscattering characteristics are strikingly similar to those of Amalthea. Veverka et al. (1981) report Amalthea's phase coefficient B for $\alpha < 40^\circ$ to be 0.042 ± 0.004 mag/deg. Assuming a linear trend from 18° to 2.5° in our data, we derive $B = 0.042 \pm 0.008$. These values are somewhat larger than is typical for satellites and asteroids. Earthbased photometry of the Galilean satellites yields $B = 0.021, 0.004, 0.019$ and 0.028 for Io, Europa, Ganymede and Callisto, respectively (Morrison and Morrison, 1977), while the Moon's phase law exhibits $B = 0.028$ (Allen, 1976). Asteroids have typical phase coefficients in the range 0.018 to 0.036 , depending strongly on taxonomic type (Bowell and Lumme, 1979). Veverka et al. report that only objects with very dark, rough surfaces, such as Phobos, Deimos and the

irregular Jovian satellite Himalia, show phase coefficients as large as Amalthea's.

In addition to the phase functions, color measurements are in quite close agreement between Amalthea and the ring. Our Jovian ring measurements are plotted against the normalized reflectance of Amalthea (Veverka et al., 1981, Fig. 5a.) in Fig. 6.12. Since both sets of measurements use Danielson et al.'s (1981) calibration factors, the values should be self-consistent, even if the overall calibration is slightly in error. Gradie et al. (1980) propose that the combination of charged particles in the Jovian magnetosphere, sulfur contamination from Io and impacts from meteoritic matter acts to darken and redden Amalthea's surface. It is therefore not surprising that the ring, residing in the same environment, should be the same color.

Similarities between spectra of the ring and Amalthea in the visible and infrared had been noted previously by groundbased observers (Smith and Reitsema, 1980; Neugebauer et al., 1981), who studied both objects in the same experiment. It appears that an accurate replica of the ring could be constructed by simply scraping off Amalthea's surface layer and spreading it around Jupiter. These consistencies provide a good indication that we are seeing backscatter from rough, macroscopic bodies, with properties quite similar to the Amalthea surface material.

If the backscattering may be attributed to the macroscopic grains, then we may estimate the optical depth τ using the

FIGURE 6.12. A comparison of reflectance spectra from the Jovian ring and Amalthea. Amalthea measurements are from Veverka et al. (1981), their Fig. 5.

procedure of Jewitt and Danielson (1981). A plausible geometric albedo for large ring particles is $k = 0.05$, the value measured by Veverka et al. (1981) for Amalthea. Interestingly, this also equals the measurements of k for Adrastea, Metis and Thebe (Synnott, 1980, 1981; Jewitt, 1982); they are presumably all darkened by the same processes. This albedo yields $\tau = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ for the ring, a number somewhat smaller than previous estimates, but in the neighborhood of that inferred for the forward-scattering grains. It is also comparable to W. Fillius' (private communication, 1980) estimate of $\tau = \text{a few} \times 10^{-6}$, based upon Pioneer 11 measurements of the ring's charged particle absorption, and applying primarily to particles centimeter-sized or larger.

Ideally, we would like to find a single size distribution which accounts for the light scattered into both low and high phase angles. Tyler et al. (1981) attempted just such a feat, using the preliminary ring measurements of Owen et al. (1979). Interestingly, the measurement they had most trouble accounting for was the 20:1 forward-to-back ratio, which was simply too small to be easily understood. The 60:1 ratio we measure would have apparently made their task easier.

As an alternative to the macroscopic-body interpretation, the large phase coefficient could arise from the same population of micron-sized grains seen in forward-scatter. This would require that the particles be quite close to spherical, since rough particles do not show the backscatter "glory" needed to account for the

large phase coefficient. Using the distribution $n(r)$ established above for spherical, micron-sized grains, the ring's properties can be duplicated with suitable choices of refractive index and upper size cutoff. Hence, based on photometry alone, this interpretation cannot be excluded.

If the tiny ring grains truly arise from ejecta off larger bodies, it is unclear how they could be then made sufficiently spherical to produce the glory. Burns et al. (1980) put forward a mechanism whereby ring grain surfaces could be smoothed, due to the electrostatic disruption of sharp surface points. However, this mechanism may be discounted now that electric charges in the ring are thought to be much smaller than had once been believed, based on dynamical (Consolmagno, 1983) and physical (Goertz and Ip, 1984) arguments.

We regard it as more likely that the micron size range contributes some small but nonzero (probably < 30%) fraction of the backscatter intensity, while the remainder comes from a larger population of dark, red macroscopic bodies. After all, some tampering with the refractive index and shape is required for micron-sized grains to mimic the backscattering behavior, whereas a larger population fits it easily. In any case, a macroscopic population is needed to explain the Pioneer 11 charged particle absorption.

As was discussed in §1.5, a population of larger bodies ("mooms") is probably needed to continually replenish the ring's

supply of micron-sized grains. These may be same macroscopic bodies now detected in backscatter. In this connection, it should be recalled that the three bright features in the ring's outer region (§4.3) appear narrower at low phase angles than at high. This is consistent with a narrowly confined band of parent bodies (visible in backscatter), enveloped by a broader cloud of their own micron-sized ejecta (visible in forward-scatter). Such a band of moons might itself be composed of the larger ejecta from the ring moons Adrastea and Metis, or, alternatively, might simply be shepherded by them.

6.7 SUMMARY

The Jovian ring reveals very different sections of its particle size distribution in forward- and backscatter. The micron-sized grains emphasized in forward-scatter appear to obey a power-law size distribution, with spectral index $p = 2.5 \pm 0.5$. This value is suggested by variations in scattered intensity with phase angle and color. The index is consistent with the expected size distribution of tiny impact ejecta from larger bodies, which then evolve under plasma drag. This population has an optical depth of $1-6 \times 10^{-6}$, for grains up to $100 \mu\text{m}$ in radius. The ring also displays a mysterious brightness asymmetry between far and near arms.

In backscattered light, macroscopic bodies become visible, which may act as the sources of the micron-sized grains. The ring

appears to be very red and to show a steep phase coefficient, which are two properties it shares with Amalthea. This set of bodies has an optical depth of 3×10^{-6} .

Apparently, each of the ring's visible populations plays a very different physical role. Precisely how the two size distributions join together cannot be established from the limited data available.

CHAPTER 7

HALO PHOTOMETRY

7.1 INTRODUCTION

Our expectation, based on theoretical arguments summarized in §1.5, is that the halo particles are generally somewhat smaller than those in the bright ring. Small particles would have larger charge-to-mass ratios for the same surface potential, and so would have a greater response to the magnetic field's vertical perturbations. However, in §5.5 we found that the halo grains cannot be too small, for then an asymmetry about the ring plane would have been seen. We now seek direct photometric information about the halo particle sizes and properties, rather than constraints based upon purely dynamical arguments.

In the forward-scatter images, the halo contributes more total light than the bright ring. Nevertheless, measuring its light-scattering properties is a formidable task, mainly because of its uncertain vertically-extended geometry. The intensity measured in any halo pixel is the sum of contributions along a line of sight, which samples points throughout the halo region. Variations in that intensity may therefore be the result of changes in geometry or phase angle, or both. For this reason, no previous investigators have attempted photometry of the halo.

In their photometric properties, smaller particles would have a broader diffraction lobe, and therefore should show a flatter scattering law between $\theta = 6^\circ$ and 3° , the range sampled by the forward-scatter images. This is qualitatively consistent with the fact that the halo shows a negligible brightening in the limb images, over a θ -range in which the main ring brightens considerably (Fig. 7.1; cf. Fig. 6.1). In these views the halo geometry seems fairly constant, as is shown in the halo "slicing" discussion of §5.2 (see Fig. 5.1), so one might infer that the phase function is roughly constant as well. This qualitative argument will be critically examined below.

If the halo grains are small enough ($X \ll 1$), then they will Rayleigh-scatter as discussed in Appendix B. In this case their scattered light will be nearly isotropic, as bright in backscatter as forward-scatter. Unfortunately, the backscatter images are not well-suited to halo detection, because scattered light from Jupiter is much larger than the main ring's light, let alone the diffuse halo's. Rayleigh-scattering grains will also show an orange-to-violet ratio of $\sim 1/4$, based on the λ^{-4} dependence of scattering cross sections in this regime (see Appendix B). This possibility may be easily tested in the color forward-scatter images.

7.2 THE HALO'S SCATTERING LAW

At first glance, Fig. 7.1 suggests that the halo does not brighten significantly between the scattering angles of 4.6° and

FIGURE 7.1. FDS 20691.27, with the halo enhanced in shades of gray and contours of scattering angle overplotted. Unlike the bright ring (cf. Fig. 6.1), the halo does not seem to brighten significantly between scattering angles of 4.6° and 3.8° .

3.8°. However, this neglects the lengthening of the line of sight through the halo as the view is shifted from the Jovian limb outward toward the ring ansa. This effect is analogous to the lengthening of lines of sight d across the ring in our edge-on views, discussed in §6.5 (see also Fig. 6.9). By this effect, the ring would brighten by 15-20% in Fig. 7.1 if it were composed of perfectly isotropic scatterers; the fact that it does not indicates instead that the ring particles must brighten by 15-20% in the other direction. This implies a photometric slope for the halo of 0.3-0.4 mag/deg in this image, which is nonzero, but smaller than the corresponding 0.6-0.7 mag/deg slope for the bright ring (see Fig. 6.4).

Clearly, it would be valuable to approach more rigorously the question of how the halo intensity varies with phase angle. This calls for a more cautious description of the ring's three-dimensional structure. Ideally, we seek the scattering behavior of the halo, including any variations with radius and elevation. We now outline a procedure which might make this possible.

First, we divide the halo into separate bins in radius R and elevation Z , and assume that the material within each bin has uniform properties, described by $\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0P(\theta)$. Recall that the linear extinction coefficient α is a measure of optical depth per unit distance along the line of sight. In this scheme, the contribution from the material within any bin to an intensity measurement is in direct proportion to d , the length of the line of sight which falls

within that bin. We define I/F_i as the intensity measured from the i^{th} pixel of an image, and d_{ij} as the distance the corresponding line of sight spends in the j^{th} geometric bin. These quantities are interrelated by

$$I/F_i = \sum_j d_{ij} \cdot \frac{\alpha \omega_0 P_j(\theta_i)}{4} \quad [7.1]$$

which is simply a restatement of [2.15]. In this relation, the d_{ij} 's are calculable from the image geometry, and the I/F_i 's are measured. We seek the values for $\alpha \omega_0 P_j(\theta)$. For the 4-6° range of θ 's in the forward-scattered images, it is probably adequate to use a linear approximation to the halo's phase function. Hence, our model becomes

$$I/F_i = \sum_j d_{ij} \cdot \frac{(A_j + B_j \cdot \theta_i)}{4} \quad [7.2]$$

where the constant coefficients A_j and B_j are to be estimated.

So far, we have neglected one further inconvenience. Since the NA frames capture a rather tiny field on the ring, there is no region in any of these forward-scatter images without a light contribution from the halo. Therefore we can make no direct measurements of the background intensity levels in any of the frames. The solution is to incorporate a separate unknown background ramp for each image into our photometric model. Finally,

$$I/F_i = \sum_j d_{ij} \cdot \frac{(A_j + B_j \theta_i)}{4} + C_k + D_k \cdot \lambda_i + E_k \cdot s_i, \quad [7.3]$$

where λ_i and s_i are the pixel coordinates (line, sample) of the i^{th} measurement, and the subscripts k refer the background coefficients C , D , and E to the specific image from which the measurement was taken.

Equation [7.3] describes a linear problem in the unknowns A - E , which may be solved by standard linear least-squares techniques. For our purposes, we divide the halo into 12 unequal geometric bins, with 4 bins in radius (bounded by $R = 90, 105, 115, 122$, and 130×10^3 km), and three elevation bins (bounded by $|Z| = 0, 1000, 3000$, and 5000 km). For this fit, we do not distinguish between positive and negative elevations. These divisions were chosen to mimic the nonuniformity of the halo, which varies more rapidly at lower elevations and near its outer edge (see §5.2). Larger numbers of bins would allow for finer resolution of the halo's structure, but would also lead to greater uncertainties, since more parameters must be fit to the limited data. A total of 270 halo I/F values have been measured from the six NA images FDS 20692.37-.57. The model requires two parameters A, B for each of 12 bins, plus three background parameters C, D, E for each frame; hence 42 parameters are to be fit simultaneously to the 270 measurements.

The success of the model may be gauged qualitatively, from a number of considerations. We expect $\alpha \tilde{\omega}_0 P(\theta) = A + B\theta$ to be

positive, for all θ within the range 4° - 6° . The values for $\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0P$ should also decrease monotonically with decreasing radius and increasing elevation. In addition, it is our hope that the slopes B/A should show some uniform behavior, possibly with trends in the different directions. By these criteria, our fits are not particularly successful, despite RMS residuals of a few percent of the halo intensity. The parameters are summarized in Table 7.1.

Several explanations for the lack of success may be listed. First, the grid system may be too coarse. Finer grids in R and Z were tried, but the larger number of parameters to fit resulted in even less consistent results. More importantly, the images may simply sample too small a range of lines of sight through the system; all of our lines of sight make the same 2° angle with the ring plane. We describe this procedure in such detail here mainly because it will be potentially useful for interpreting future Galileo images of the halo.

Nevertheless, one should not write off the results of this procedure too hastily. Note that the bins closest to the ring (where we know the halo to be densest) are consistently positive, and of the same order as those found in the halo contour maps (Fig. 5.6). They also show a consistently negative slope, as is expected for diffraction. If we weight the denser bins more heavily, by A^2 , we find a mean slope B/A over all the bins of -0.40 deg^{-1} , or 0.44 mag/deg . If we instead weight them by $|A|$, the mean slope is -0.44 deg^{-1} , or 0.48 mag/deg . These values are not vastly

TABLE 7.1: Linear fit to the halo photometry

		PHOTOMETRIC PARAMETERS (A, B, B/A) ^a				
E L E V A T I O N Z ^b	5.	-0.05	0.45	-0.91	1.79	
		-0.23	0.19	1.65	-1.54	
		4.29	0.43	-1.82	-0.86	
	3.	-0.17	0.83	-0.27	1.32	
		0.09	-0.36	1.32	-2.17	
		-0.54	-0.44	-4.79	-0.72	
	1.	0.86	3.84	4.08	6.89	
		1.05	-1.05	-0.14	-3.30	
		1.22	-0.27	-0.03	-0.48	
	0.					
		90.	105.	115.	122.	130.
		RADIUS R ^b				

^aValues for A, B and B/A are listed vertically for each geometric bin. A and B have units of 10^{-9} km^{-1} and $10^{-9} \text{ km}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$, respectively, and are evaluated at $\theta = 5^\circ$. Hence, the model for $\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0^P$ based on these values is:

$$\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0^P(\theta) = (A + B \cdot (\theta - 5^\circ)) \times 10^{-9} \text{ km}^{-1}.$$

^bThe R and Z values (in units of 10^3 km) which separate each of the twelve geometric bins.

different from the estimate of 0.3-0.4 mag/deg arrived at earlier. In sum, we can say that the halo brightens by 0.4 ± 0.1 mag/deg between scattering angles of 6° and 4° .

One other aspect of the halo's scattering properties needs to be mentioned. Examination of the isophotes near the ansa in WA frame FDS 20693.02 (see Fig. 3.2) shows that, within the arms of the ring, the halo brightens toward the far arm by $\sim 10\%$. This effect is not consistent with a vertical halo offset, because the isophotes outside the ring in this image are symmetric above and below the ring plane. It is, however, consistent with the near/far arm asymmetry found in the bright ring in this same frame (see §§6.2-3). The effect is visible in enhancements of the NA mosaic frames near the ansa (FDS 20692.49,.53) as well, confirming it as a ring feature. Apparently, whatever process yields asymmetry in the bright ring's light also acts in the nearby regions of the halo.

7.3 COLOR PHOTOMETRY

One procedure does exist whereby uncertainties in the halo geometry may be eliminated. The forward-scattered Jovian limb images come in pairs (FDS 20691.27/.31, 20691.35/.39) with similar geometry but different smears. The ratio of intensities from these pairs therefore provides reliable color information.

Noise in the halo is still a problem, so it is desirable to average over large numbers of pixels before the ratio is taken.

For these measurements, we generate profiles which are essentially identical to those of §5.3, which were used to constrain the halo's asymmetry. We take profiles perpendicular to the ring plane, this time being careful to capture regions of identical geometry in each of the image pairs.

In Fig. 7.2 we show one of the resultant orange-to-violet scan ratios, from FDS 20691.27 and .31. As one might expect, the ratio becomes noisier with increasing $|Z|$, because smaller intensities must be divided. One might wish to interpret a change in the color ratio with elevation as evidence for a variation in the size distribution (cf. §6.4); however, we have found that the graphed ratio can either increase or decrease with elevation, depending very strongly on the background intensity level assumed. This level has been determined by fitting a ramp to points on opposite sides of the halo region in the images, and subtracting. However, the background becomes fractionally more important as halo intensity diminishes, for the same reason that noise becomes more important. Hence, we are unable to identify a significant color ratio variation with elevation.

Nevertheless, in a central region identified by $|Z| \lesssim 3000$ km on the graph, the ratio appears to be a quite uniform 1.6 ± 0.2 . This value is measured on both image pairs, and is relatively independent of the background level assumed.

FIGURE 7.2. The halo's orange-to-violet intensity ratio, plotted as a function of mean elevation Z from the ring plane. Scan geometry is described in Fig. 5.7. The ratio is a nearly-constant 1.6 ± 0.2 for smaller $|Z|$. The trends at higher $|Z|$ depend strongly upon the background contributions, and therefore cannot be believed; we cannot identify a significant variation in color ratio with Z .

7.4 THE BACKSCATTER SEARCH

We have made a determined effort to locate some trace of the halo in the Voyager backscattered images. This is an important measurement for determining whether any significant number of Rayleigh-scatterers is present in the halo. The largest obstacle is the predominance of planet-scattered light, which contaminates every one of these frames. Uncertainties in the background levels are dwarfed by this light source. The problem could be partly eliminated if our images captured regions of dark sky; with a reliable dark sky reference, the halo's tiny incremental contribution might be measurable. Unfortunately, most of the backscatter images are from the NA camera. They capture only a small field of view around the narrow ring, in which any halo contribution is fairly uniform throughout, and therefore unrecognizable. The best NA backscattered candidate is the discovery image, owing to its 11-minute exposure time. However, this image captures only the outermost 7000 km of the ring system, and so misses entirely the region in which we have seen the halo.

Nevertheless, one WA backscattered image exists: FDS 20630.53 (see Fig. 1.5). This is a 15-s exposure of the ring from close to the ring plane. Contamination from the lit Jovian disk, off-field by the equivalent of less than 200 pixels, saturates the image near the lower right but is more uniform through the remainder of the frame. A small halo glow would be very hard to find underneath this light. Nevertheless, we follow our usual procedure of fitting

a quadratic function of line and sample to the light near the ring, and subtracting. The resultant image, contrast-enhanced, is shown in Fig. 7.3. Slight bulges in the isophotes are seen near the ring plane, which are crudely consistent with the halo's putative form. They are only barely visible in the frame before the subtraction. The I/F value from this bulge is $\sim 2 \times 10^{-6}$ at $\theta = 18^\circ$, which is 20% of the halo's forward-scatter brightness. However, since we cannot be certain that this structure was not introduced by our processing, we interpret this number instead as an upper limit on the halo's light in backscatter.

7.5 INTERPRETATIONS

The most obvious conclusion to be reached from these measurements is that the halo grains are not Rayleigh-scatterers. Three independent lines of argument lead to this same result. First, the halo brightens in forward-scatter by ~ 0.4 mag/deg near $\theta = 4^\circ$; this brightening, though uncertain, is incompatible with the nearly flat Rayleigh-scattering phase function (see Appendix B, [B.3]). Second, the orange/violet ratio of 1.6 ± 0.2 is distant from the expected ratio of ~ 0.25 . Third, the halo is fainter by at least a factor of 5 in backscatter than in forward-scatter. Taken together, these properties exclude Rayleigh-scatterers from playing any prominent role in the halo. Halo grains must be larger than size parameter $X \approx 1$, or $r \approx 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. In a sense, this merely confirms what we had already suspected on dynamical grounds, summarized in §5.4.

FIGURE 7.3. FDS 20630.53 with a steep background model subtracted, in order to search for the halo in backscatter. It has been colored in discrete shades of gray. The isophote bulges near the ring may suggest a halo detection, although we cannot exclude the possibility that this feature was introduced by the processing. An upper limit of $I/F < 2 \times 10^{-6}$ may be placed on the halo in this frame.

The color ratio is the best-constrained of the halo's photometric properties. The orange-to-violet ratio of 1.6 ± 0.2 is nearly identical to the analogous bright ring measurement of 1.64 ± 0.11 (§6.4). If this value may be ascribed to a power-law size distribution, then its index p must fall into the same range (2.5 ± 0.5) as for the bright ring. The halo's phase function slope is comparable to that of the bright ring, though slightly flatter. This might suggest an enhancement of smaller grains in the halo over the bright ring, such as in a distribution with a slightly steeper power law (larger p), or one in which some of the larger grains have been lost. Unfortunately, the data simply do not permit a more refined interpretation.

As a final comparison to the bright ring, we estimate the halo's normal optical depth. This may be accomplished by integrating $\alpha\tilde{\omega}_0P$ in the vertical direction, using the halo cross sections obtained in §5.2. The result is a peak halo value of $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P(\theta) = 3 \times 10^{-5}$ at $R = 110,000$ km, based on FDS 20691.27 at $\theta \approx 4$. This is comparable to $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P = 4 \times 10^{-5}$ for the bright ring, from the same image (see Fig. 6.4). If we allow the questionable assumption that the halo and ring size distributions are the same, at least in micron-sized grains, then the normal optical depths τ of the two systems are also nearly equal. Indeed, it follows that the halo, by virtue of its larger ring-plane area, actually holds a larger number of particles than the ring.

Exactly what happens at the bright ring's inner boundary to "turn on" the halo's vertical thickening is unknown. Since both systems have comparable optical depth, we cannot rely on inter-particle collisions to make much difference. How is it that, within a radial distance of a few thousand kilometers, the physical properties of the ring system change so markedly? Since sizes do not appear to differ drastically between the two systems, the difference must instead be in their charges or in the properties of the magnetic field.

Schaffer and Burns (1984) note that the magnetic perturbations on charged grains increase inward from the ring, in part because higher moments of the field become important, and in part because the grains orbit at higher speeds with respect to the corotating field. Although these conditions undoubtedly do play a role, their onset is too gradual to explain the rather sudden change from ring to halo observed. These investigators also note the presence of a weak Lorentz resonance near the ring/halo transition, which may help to activate the halo's thickening.

Changes in particle charges could be understood in terms of recent work on the mutual shielding of grains within a dusty plasma, by Goertz and Ip (1984; cf. Grün et al., 1984; Havnes et al., 1984). They report that the surface potential of an individual grain in such an environment is reduced, relative to what it should have in isolation, by a factor of $1 + x$, where

$$x = 4\pi N r \lambda_D^2 \quad [7.4]$$

In this expression, N is local space density of particles, and λ_D is the plasma Debye length. Although the ring and halo have comparable optical depths, and therefore similar surface densities, they obviously have very different spatial densities. The halo is extended by $\sim 10^4$ km, whereas the ring is thinner than 30 km. This gives an immediate factor of 300 in their relative N 's, but since the ring's thickness is unresolved, the factor may be much larger still.

It is helpful to rewrite [7.4] into a more transparent form. Using a standard expression for λ_D (Goertz and Ip, 1984), and $\tau \approx N\pi r^2 h$, where h is the ring's thickness, the equation for x becomes

$$x = 0.22 \left(\frac{\tau}{10^{-6}}\right) \left(\frac{r}{\mu\text{m}}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{h}{\text{km}}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{kT_e}{\text{eV}}\right) \left(\frac{n}{\text{cm}^{-3}}\right)^{-1} \quad [7.5]$$

Here k is Boltzmann's constant, T_e is the plasma's electron temperature and n is its density. The final two terms in this expression have never been measured at the ring, and so are extremely uncertain. However, very crude extrapolations of Voyager measurements near Io (Belcher, 1983) yield $kT_e = 1\text{-}100$ eV and $n = 10\text{-}100 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For these values, x is of order one in the bright ring. Thus, it is not implausible that a change in h from ~ 1 km

to $\sim 10^4$ km at the ring/halo boundary can make the difference between a large x and a small one. Turning this equation around, it may be useful for placing better constraints on the local plasma properties.

The key to why the ring/halo transition occurs at a specific location may have to do with the larger bodies assumed to be present within the ring, based on backscatter photometry (§6.6), charged particle absorption (Ip, 1980) and theoretical grounds (Burns et al., 1980; Grün et al., 1980). Burns et al. (1984) point out that the bright ring's current radial width is consistent with parent bodies which have diffused from a more confined region over the age of the solar system. Hence, the ring's radial width may simply reflect the distribution of larger bodies. Such a population of parent bodies, with optical depth $\tau = \text{a few} \times 10^{-6}$, is inadequate to shield the tiny ring grains itself. However, it may damp their motions (to keep h small) and also absorb the local plasma (to keep n small), thereby ensuring that x is large and so the tiny grains are effectively uncharged.

However, those grains which leak past the ring's inner edge find themselves unprotected by the larger bodies. They would quickly acquire the free-space potential of ~ -10 V, and then be perturbed to fill the halo region (see §5.4). In this model, the overall size distributions in the ring and halo would be similar, though magnetic perturbations would distribute smaller grains to higher elevations in the halo. This simple description, though

lacking in some theoretical details, is consistent with all of the ring and halo measurements we have acquired.

7.6 SUMMARY

We have obtained three separate measurements of the Jovian halo's photometric properties. First, its phase function reveals a slope of 0.4 ± 0.1 mag/deg in forward-scatter ($\theta = 4-6^\circ$). Second, it has an orange-to-violet intensity ratio of 1.6 ± 0.2 . Third, it is no more than 20% as bright in backscatter as in forward-scatter.

Each of these measurements is incompatible with Rayleigh-scattering, so halo particle radii may be constrained to $> 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. In comparison to the bright ring, the color is identical, suggesting that a power-law size distribution with the same index p ($= 2.5 \pm 0.5$) is present. However, the phase function slope is smaller, indicating that the halo may be relatively enhanced in the tiniest grains. Integration of the halo cross sections in §5.2 yields a normal optical depth for the halo which is quite similar to that for the bright ring.

The fundamental difference between the two systems probably lies in the charges on their constituent grains. Interparticle shielding may maintain low charges in the ring, but is ineffective in the halo. There the grains have sufficient charge to be dispersed by the vertical perturbations of the magnetic field.

CHAPTER 8

JUPITER'S "GOSSAMER" RING

8.1 DISCOVERY

The WA ansa image of the Jovian ring, FDS 20693.02, provides an excellent illustration of the importance of a careful dark current subtraction in Voyager image processing. Using the standard IPL dark current frame, this image reveals an enormous intensity gradient through the regions of dark sky, from negative intensities at the upper right corner to large positive intensities (greater than the halo) at lower left (Fig. 8.1).

Our first correction to this problem involved fitting a smooth function to the background and subtracting it out, to ensure some uniformity across the frame. After this correction, a residual stripe of excess intensity persisted, extending out beyond the ring ansa. It could have been easily ignored (and was by previous investigators), except that its geometry was perfectly consistent with an extension to the bright ring, running outward to ~200,000 km. The presence of such a feature is only hinted at before the background subtraction (Fig. 8.1). Although its geometry is suggestive, the feature's low intensity, combined with the data's extensive reprocessing history, made its reality as a component of the ring system questionable. After all, one can

FIGURE 8.1. An enhancement of the background in FDS 20693.02, after the standard dark current subtraction. The background intensity increases considerably toward lower left, but a faint stripe can be seen extending out beyond the ring ansa.

scarcely imagine how much unreal structure could be inserted into Voyager images with enough "refined" processing.

To reassess its reality, we must return to the raw Voyager data. Recognizing that the large gradient was probably introduced by the dark current, we requested that IPL create a new version, using another dark current of appropriate characteristics taken only 25 hours previous to the image (FDS 20661.01). The resultant image shows none of the background gradient problems previously noted, and the presence of a very faint external feature is unambiguous (Fig. 8.2). Although it shows a mean intensity of only one-half the overall noise level, it covers such a large region of the image (~30,000 pixels) that its integrated signal-to-noise ratio is ~110. It is definitely not a statistical fluke of the imaging system.

One possibility which cannot be overlooked is that this feature is merely the ghost of a previous WA image. However, the previous WA frame (FDS 20691.47) was of the dark side of Jupiter, and shows nothing resembling this structure. In addition, we have verified (Collins, private communication, 1983) that no untransmitted image was exposed in the short intervening period. Hence the possibility that this feature is a quirk of the Voyager vidicon may be safely ruled out.

Ideally, confirmation of this discovery would come from a second Voyager image showing the same structure. In Fig. 8.2 it is quickly lost under the glow of the much brighter halo, and so we

FIGURE 8.2. An enhancement of the background in FDS 20693.02, after subtraction of the dark current taken closest in time to the image. The strong background gradient has vanished, and a ring extension is quite apparent.

can only expect to detect it beyond the bright ring's ansa. The backscattered images are not promising candidates, for here the halo is invisible, and even the bright ring itself is difficult to detect. We have unearthed a previously-ignored Voyager image, as a promising candidate for revealing this feature. The planned NA mosaic of Jupiter's ring consisted of seven sequential frames, designated FDS 20692.37-20693.01 (see Fig. 1.7). However, the last frame fell beyond the ansa by a small amount, and so previously-published mosaics (Owen et al., 1979, Fig. 5) comprise only the other six. This seventh (FDS 20693.01), exposed only 48 seconds before the WA ansa image, should have captured this external ring. Indeed, its field of view coincides with the central region of the WA frame (Fig. 8.3).

Before any special processing, this frame shows some extra intensity at the upper right, qualitatively similar to what one would expect from the diffuse ring. Unfortunately, uncertainty in the dark current leads to a large intensity offset from zero throughout the field. As always, we must subtract out the background light, based on dark sky regions in the image. Only the lower portion of this frame falls outside the presumed ring, so we fit intensities to a linear function of line and sample in this region, and then subtract from the entire frame. The result (Fig. 8.4) is an image similar both qualitatively and quantitatively to the coincident portion of the WA frame (see box in Fig. 8.3).

This image could not, in and of itself, have been interpreted

FIGURE 8.3. A closeup of the WA image, with the outline of NA frame FDS 20693.01 plotted. Also shown are contours of radius, in 20×10^3 km steps from 140×10^3 km.

FIGURE 8.4. Image FDS 20693.01, after subtraction of a linear background function (see text). Note its similarity to the rectangle in Fig. 8.3, including star locations.

as evidence for an additional ring, since our background subtraction required some knowledge of the ring already. However, the image is certainly consistent with the feature we believe that we have discovered in the WA frame.

One additional body of information may potentially bear on this ring: the Pioneer 11 charged particle absorption data, which detected the bright ring. The data acquired very close to Jupiter have never been completely unravelled (Fillius, 1976; private communication, 1980), and this feature might be part of the reason why. Indeed, additional absorbers appear to be present between Amalthea and the ring. Nevertheless, for further high-quality data about this extremely faint structure, we will have to await Galileo's arrival at Jupiter.

8.2 STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION

It may seem at first that gleaning further information from an image that only shows the ring at 0.5σ would be a hopeless task. However, acting in our favor is the large number of pixels which this "gossamer" ring covers.

We can generate radial profiles of the ring by simply binning each pixel as a function of its orbital radius and then averaging intensity, much as we did in §4.2 for the bright ring. Calculated radius contours are plotted atop the ring in Fig. 8.3. We must assume here that the ring is azimuthally symmetric, relatively thin and in the equatorial plane, for the profile to be meaningful. The results are shown in Fig. 8.5 for both the WA and NA images. The

FIGURE 8.5. Radial profiles of the external Jovian ring, based upon WA image FDS 20693.02 and NA image FDS 20693.01. In the latter case, the background contribution is increasingly uncertain for smaller radii. The WA scan reveals a distinct peak centered on synchronous orbit, which the NA is too smeared to show.

absolute scaling on the NA image is more uncertain, because we must extrapolate the background fit from the bottom region to the top of the frame. It is also smeared more severely, by either 4000 or 7000 km, depending on the stars' direction of motion within their hairpin-shaped trails (see Appendix A).

Locations of the relevant satellites, as well as synchronous orbit, are also specified in the figure. It appears that the ring decreases in intensity rather uniformly with radius, with possible slight variations superimposed. Most of the ring is interior to the orbit of Amalthea, though some of it extends to 210,000 km, and perhaps out to the neighborhood of Thebe. Its overall mean brightness is $\sim 1/20$ that of the main ring. If optical depths scale directly with intensities, then this ring has $\tau \approx 10^{-7}$, which is comparable to Saturn's E ring.

The most notable feature is a 20% enhancement centered at 160,000 km, quite close to synchronous orbit (159,400 km). We estimate this to be significant at the 4σ level. In fact, it was first observed visually in the image, and only later found to fall near synchronous orbit; it can be seen faintly in Fig. 8.2 (squinting may help!). The feature is ~ 5000 km wide in the scan, but may actually be much narrower. It is not visible on the NA frame, where noise and image smear are larger.

The assumption of a thin ring is essential to assigning a single radius to each pixel in the image. If the ring is vertically extended, then each pixel represents an integrated line of sight

through the system, along which a range of radii and elevations are sampled. This could lead to substantial errors in the radial scale shown. A rough upper limit of ~ 2000 km can be placed on the ring thickness from its visible geometry. Though not strongly-constrained in vertical extent, this ring is distinctly thinner than the halo.

The image shows some evidence for a variation in brightness with phase angle over the 7° - 6° scattering angle range sampled. In Fig. 8.6 we plot ring intensities measured at a constant orbital radius, versus scattering angle. Each data point is an average over 150-200 pixels. The ring appears to brighten by nearly a factor of two. If we can attribute this behavior to diffraction by spheres of a single size, then that size is $\lambda \approx 20$, or $r \approx 1.5 \mu\text{m}$. Of course, any size determination from such a tiny range of θ is not particularly meaningful, but the presence of micron-sized grains is certainly suggested, as in the main ring.

We have searched for a trace of this ring in three edge-on backscattered views (FDS 16368.19, 20630.52, 20630.53). By averaging over large numbers of pixels, we can limit the external ring's backscatter brightness to less than 1% that of the bright ring. This is somewhat smaller than the forward-scatter intensity ratio of $\sim 5\%$ between these rings, and suggests that relatively fewer of this gossamer ring's particles are macroscopic. At the same time, this ratio also rules out a significant population of Rayleigh-scatterers in the ring.

FIGURE 8.6. Crude photometry of the external ring, based on measurements taken from the WA image, at constant radius. The noise level is apparent from the point scatter, but a brightening trend is nevertheless revealed. Single-particle phase functions (size parameter X) are overplotted, and $X = 20$ fits to within the scatter.

8.3. DYNAMICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This faint ring is among the most puzzling features of Jupiter's ring system. In part, this may be simply a consequence of the dearth of information available. As in the other components, the tiny grains cannot be expected to survive forever, and so they must be continually replenished from some source, seen or unseen.

Two moons, Amalthea and Thebe, are obvious choices as potential ring sources. According to the studies of Burns and Showalter (1983; see also Burns et al., 1984), micrometeoroid impacts into satellites of radius r (larger than some minimum size) yield ejecta in proportion to $r^{-1/4}$. Larger satellites exhibit a greater cross section, but their increased escape velocities prevent more material from leaving the surface; hence smaller satellites can release more ejecta. Amalthea ($r = 120$ km) and Thebe ($r = 80$ km; Synnott, 1980) should each release ~60% as much ejecta as Adrastea ($r = 12$ km) or Metis ($r = 20$ km). Since the external ring is 11 times broader in radial extent than the bright ring, debris from Amalthea and Thebe might be expected to be $60\%/11 \approx 1/20$ as bright when spread uniformly. Though possibly a mere numerical coincidence, this closely agrees with what is observed. In reality, the issue is more complex. First, since Adrastea and Metis lie within the Roche limit, material from their surfaces will have a somewhat easier time escaping, and has probably been underestimated. Second, we do not claim that either

pair of satellites is responsible for all of the fine material in its nearby ring.

In order to understand particle motions after ejection, we must consider once again the relevant drag forces. Specifically, we consider Poynting-Robertson (PR) drag and plasma drag, which are believed to dominate in the bright ring. The timescale for evolution by PR drag is given by Burns et al. (1984, eq. [11])

$$T_{PR} = 10^3 \left(\frac{R_p}{AU} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\rho}{g \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right) \left(\frac{r}{\mu\text{m}} \right) Q_{PR}^{-1} \text{ yr} . \quad [8.1]$$

where R_p is the planet's orbital radius, ρ is the grain density, r is the grain radius and Q_{PR} is an efficiency factor, of order one. Assuming Jupiter's orbit and a density of 2 g cm^{-3} , this yields an evolution timescale

$$T_{PR} = 3 \times 10^4 \left(\frac{r}{\mu\text{m}} \right) \text{ yr} . \quad [8.2]$$

PR drag always causes orbital collapse.

Plasma drag, on the other hand, always evolves material away from the synchronous orbit. Its timescale is considerably more difficult to estimate, because the plasma properties this close to Jupiter have been measured only once (by Pioneer 11) and then not well. An estimate for it is (Burns et al., 1984, eq. [12])

$$T_{PD} = \frac{2\rho r \xi}{3\rho_p dv} , \quad [8.3]$$

where ρ_p is the local plasma density, dv is the velocity difference between a grain and the plasma, and ξ is an efficiency factor, which is of order one for uncharged grains. The plasma density can only be guessed at; assuming ρ_p to be dominated by heavy ions and extrapolating from measurements near Io (Belcher, 1983), a rough value of $\sim 10^{-20}$ g cm $^{-3}$ seems reasonable, perhaps to within a factor of ten. This yields

$$T_{PD} = 4 \times 10^3 \left(\frac{r}{\mu\text{m}} \right) \left(\frac{dv}{\text{km s}^{-1}} \right)^{-1} \text{ yr} . \quad [8.4]$$

The velocity difference dv depends quite strongly on the orbital radius R considered, because the grains are in Keplerian orbits while the plasma is tied to Jupiter's rotating magnetic field. The velocities of grains (v_g) and plasma (v_p) may be written

$$v_g = 35.6 \left(\frac{R}{10^5 \text{ km}} \right)^{-1/2} \text{ km/s} , \quad [8.5]$$

and

$$v_p = 17.7 \left(\frac{R}{10^5 \text{ km}} \right) \text{ km/s} . \quad [8.6]$$

As expected, these velocities match at synchronous orbit, $R = 159400$ km. At this location plasma does not drift with respect to the ring material, and so exerts no drag; T_{PD} therefore becomes infinite. In Fig. 8.7, we plot T_{PD} , for $r = 1 \mu\text{m}$, as a function of orbital radius.

FIGURE 8.7. A plot of the plasma drag timescale for particles of 1 μm radius in circumjovian orbit. The enhancement of this timescale around synchronous orbit, within the external ring, is apparent. The Poynting-Robertson timescale, at $\sim 3 \times 10^4$ yr, is off-scale.

The bright feature at synchronous orbit is particularly mysterious, since plasma drag should pull material away from this radius, not toward it. However, the divergence of T_{PD} is important, for it suggests that material placed at this orbit will remain for a longer time than that placed elsewhere; if source bodies for the visible grains fill the entire ring region, then an enhancement near synchronous would be expected. Even the addition of other drag forces should not nullify this, for there will always exist a point just beyond synchronous where the forces, acting in opposite directions, cancel. As a result, a precise measurement of this feature's location would constrain the importance of other drag forces with respect to plasma drag.

Another mysterious aspect of this ring is its limited vertical extent, $\lesssim 2000$ km. One would expect the same processes which charge the halo's grains to be acting here, so vertical thickening should ensue. With such a low optical depth, it is unlikely that interparticle shielding can keep the grain charges small. One important difference between this ring and the halo is the amplitude of the magnetic forces. Here the dipole field component is smaller by a factor of ~ 3 , while higher-order moments are reduced even further. At the same time, grain velocities with respect to the corotating field are much smaller here, in the neighborhood of synchronous orbit. These two circumstances combine to reduce the magnetic perturbations, and hence the ring's vertical extent, by a factor of ~ 10 compared to the halo. This would place the ring's

thickness within its measured upper limit.

Although some aspects of this gossamer ring may be comprehended, overall it remains an enigma. But at least, it may have a dynamical counterpart at Saturn. A very faint outward extension to Saturn's A ring has been discovered by careful statistical analysis of the Voyager 2 photopolarimeter stellar occultation data (Graps et al., 1984), while evidence for it was also found in the Voyager images, using enhancement techniques similar to those described herein (Burns et al., 1983). Like its Jovian counterpart, it extends from a much brighter ring (Ring A) outward to the vicinity of a satellite (Atlas), while decreasing continuously in optical depth. Its mean τ is $\sim 1/40$ of the outer A ring value. However, in its radial width (~ 900 km) and overall optical depth (~ 0.01) it is very different from the ring at Jupiter. Whether these structures have a common dynamical basis is uncertain, because as yet neither is understood.

8.4 SUMMARY

The first thing to be said about the external gossamer ring is that it does exist; it appears at the 110σ level in one Voyager image, and its presence is hinted at in another.

The ring appears to decrease rather steadily in brightness from the main ring outward to the neighborhood of Amalthea and Thebe. Its only notable feature is a bright hump near synchronous orbit. On the average, it is $\sim 5\%$ as bright as the main ring in

forward-scatter, but less than 1% as bright in backscatter. A brightening of the ring with phase angle suggests that it holds a population of diffracting, micron-sized grains, much like the other Jovian ring system components. Its thickness may be constrained to less than 2000 km.

As in the bright ring, this ring's visible grains are probably maintained as ejecta from a population of parent bodies distributed through the region. The diminished plasma drag rate near synchronous orbit may account for the visible feature there. The ring's thickness is probably on the order of 1000 km, which is too thin to be observed directly, but consistent with expected magnetic perturbations on the constituent grains.

CHAPTER 9

THE JOVIAN RING SYSTEM: A REVISIONIST VIEW

9.1 OBSERVATIONAL RESULTS

This study has revealed a number of previously-unidentified physical properties of Jupiter's ring system. It consists of three components: the bright ring, halo and external "gossamer" ring. The inner disk component, reported by previous investigators, is not present at a detectable level. We may exclude any disk which is more than 1% as bright as the main ring in forward-scatter.

The bright ring has an outer boundary at 129130 ± 100 km, slightly beyond the orbit of Adrastea. This value is the same in forward- and backscatter, and shows no evidence for a ring eccentricity ($e \lesssim 10^{-3}$). The ring's outer boundary transition region has a radial width of 100 ± 100 km. Although an abrupt ring boundary cannot be rigorously excluded by these data, it is more likely that the ring edge has a nonzero width, unlike the denser rings of Saturn and Uranus, which terminate abruptly. The structure in the ring's outer 2000 km is dominated by three evenly-spaced brightness features, centered at 127600, 128250 and 128850 km. Metis and Adrastea lie just outside the first and third of these and may be associated dynamically. We have been unable to improve upon the upper limit of 30 km on the ring's thickness

reported previously (Smith et al., 1979a).

The main ring contains a population of micron-sized grains, which are well-modelled by a power-law size distribution with index $p = 2.5 \pm 0.5$. These grains account for an optical depth τ of a few $\times 10^{-6}$. A comparable optical depth may be associated with macroscopic bodies, which are emphasized in backscatter. They have rough surfaces and are distinctly red, much like the surface of Amalthea. These bodies may act as the sources for the numerous micron-sized grains seen.

The bright ring's inner boundary region is centered near 122,000 km, although it spans a radial distance of ~ 2000 km. In this vicinity the ring connects with the vertically-extended halo. This halo is symmetric about the ring plane, but extends for $\sim 10,000$ km above and below it. It thickens gradually with decreasing distance from Jupiter, but disappears near a radius of 90,000 km, fully 20,000 km above the Jovian cloudtops. The amount of material in the halo appears to diminish exponentially with elevation, showing a maximum scale height of ~ 3000 km, near a radius of 110,000 km.

The halo's light-scattering properties differ in a small but significant manner from those of the bright ring. This suggests that the particle size distributions in the two systems, at least for micron-sized grains, are similar but not identical; the halo probably has fewer large grains. The halo has not been reliably detected in backscattered light.

A faint outward extension to the bright ring has been discovered in a single Voyager image, while a second image hints at its presence. This ring is roughly 5% as bright as the main ring. It shows a steady decrease in scattered intensity with radius, terminating near a radius of 210,000 km, which is between Amalthea and Thebe. One significant additional feature is present: a narrow 20% brightness enhancement, centered on synchronous orbit. The ring brightens by a factor of two in the range of phase angles sampled, suggesting once again diffraction by a population of micron-sized grains.

9.2 THEORETICAL SUMMARY

The new determinations of the Jovian ring system's physical properties, summarized above, bear strongly on the conclusions of various previous theoretical studies. In previous chapters we have tried to place our results within a theoretical context. Here we simply summarize the primary physical processes which appear to be at work within the ring.

The bright Jovian ring is probably defined by a population of macroscopic bodies, which act as sources for the numerous micron-sized particles in the ring, and thereby define the ring's structure. Observational evidence for this population comes from Pioneer 11 measurements of charged particle absorption (Ip, 1980), and also from the ring's backscatter properties (§6.6). This population has an optical depth of $\sim 3 \times 10^{-6}$, which corresponds

to a cross-sectional area of $\sim 2 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$. For comparison, Adrastea and Metis have about one-tenth this area, so they should directly perturb the local mean brightness by roughly 10%. This is consistent with the amplitudes of the visible ring features just inside their orbits (§4.3).

The power-law size distribution of the micron-sized grains (§6.4) may be a consequence of their origin as collisional ejecta. Grün et al. (1980) report that high-velocity collisional ejecta are found to have index $p = 3.4$. However, after ejection, the more rapid orbital evolution of the smaller grains under plasma drag (Burns et al., 1984) would then act to flatten the distribution, reducing p to 2.4. This is quite consistent with our determination of $p = 2.5 \pm 0.5$.

The source of the impacting particles into the larger ring bodies is a matter of some dispute. Burns et al. (1980, 1984) estimate that the local micrometeoroid flux is sufficient to maintain the ring, while Grün et al. (1980; see also Morfill et al., 1980a-d) invoke an additional flux of dust grains released by volcanoes on Io. The flux from either source is highly uncertain, and the latter source may not exist at all (Burns et al., 1984). Historically, one of the principal motivations behind the Grün et al. model was the belief that the bright ring's particle size distribution was narrowly peaked near $r = 2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. These investigators believed that the limited size range could only be accounted for by an incoming flux of uniform, small projectiles, and the

presumed Io source fit the bill. Since we now believe that a power-law actually describes the ring grains, the need to invoke an Io source is eliminated.

Within the bright ring, the density of particles may be sufficient for interparticle shielding to reduce surface potentials to a negligible level (§7.5; Goertz and Ip, 1984; see also Grün et al., 1984). Unfortunately, to prove this requires much greater knowledge of the ring population and thickness, as well as the local plasma properties, than is currently available. Nevertheless, the ring's upper limit on thickness (30 km) requires that magnetic perturbations on the ring grains be negligible.

Drag forces, particularly plasma drag and Poynting-Robertson drag, steadily decay the orbits of the tiny visible grains. If these forces act on timescales briefer than sputtering and erosion (Burns et al., 1984), then the micron-sized particles will have an unaltered size distribution as they slowly evolve past the inner boundary of the large population. Here they will lose their shielding, acquire an equilibrium surface potential, and begin to respond to the vertical perturbations of the magnetic field (§§7.5, 5.4). In this manner they become part of the halo. Closer to the planet, the increased velocity with respect to the magnetic field, and the heightened importance of non-dipole field components, will also play a role (Schaffer and Burns, 1984). If the timescales for inward decay and vertical distribution are comparable, then the halo will thicken with decreasing radius, as is observed (§§3, 5.2).

The halo grains follow Keplerian orbits which are only weakly perturbed by the magnetic field. This follows from the absence of any halo asymmetry about the ring plane (§5.3), and also from the apparent grain sizes, based on their photometry (§7.5). At the same time, they continue to evolve inward. Since smaller grains have larger charge-to-mass ratios, they should be distributed further in elevation than large ones; unfortunately, the expected variation of size with elevation cannot be detected in our data. Once the grains reach the Lorentz resonance near $90\text{-}100 \times 10^3$ km (Schaffer and Burns, 1984), they become widely dispersed in elevation and are eventually lost to the system, perhaps by entering the Jovian atmosphere (§5.4).

The above description, albeit not unique, is consistent with nearly every observation of Jovian ring made thus far. Many of the parameters of the Jovian environment are not well-constrained (e.g., plasma properties, micrometeoroid flux), so we have not attempted to make the model more quantitative here.

Nevertheless, a number of important theoretical questions remain. If the ring's embedded satellites enhance the ring brightness nearby, as seems likely (§4.3), why is a radial offset found between their orbits and the features? Ejecta velocities and drag forces likely play a role here (Burns and Showalter, 1983). The origin of the brightness asymmetry, found in both the main ring and nearby halo (§§6.3, 7.2), is also mysterious. Since it is present in both systems, it presumably relates to a property they

share. Any theory involving the magnetic field should be able to predict the longitude where the asymmetry is largest, which could be compared to the observations. Finally, a simple explanation should be sought for the exponential density distribution with Z in the halo (§5.4), which may in part be a consequence of its particle size distribution.

In the above model we have neglected the external ring, primarily because it is baffling in nearly every respect (§8.3). Its synchronous feature strongly suggests that some interaction with the plasma is taking place, but the nature of that interaction is unclear. Throughout, the sources, sinks and even the evolving forces acting on the visible grains need to be identified, though the information currently available is probably inadequate for this task.

9.3 FUTURE OBSERVATIONS

The Galileo spacecraft, scheduled to reach Jupiter in 1988, will provide the next opportunity for significant new insights into the Jovian ring system (Johnson and Yeates, 1983). Its nominal 20-month mission on a rosette of very elliptical orbits includes ~12 passes through the inner Jovian system, with a close satellite encounter during each such pass. It will carry a sophisticated CCD camera, with a field of view quite comparable to the Voyager NA frame (Veverka, private communication, 1984). The imaging system will have greater sensitivity, and negligible

background and geometric distortion problems, compared to its Voyager counterpart. Also, since shorter exposures are permitted by its more sensitive camera, smear will be less of a problem.

It should be noted that most of the Jovian ring images were taken at distances of $\sim 20 R_J$, when the spacecraft was between the orbits of Ganymede and Callisto. This is a region through which the Galileo spacecraft will pass regularly, so countless images of fields comparable to the NA Voyager frames may be acquired by Galileo. Indeed, views comparable to the WA images may be taken from as far as $150 R_J$, where it will be unnecessary to make tradeoffs between the ring and other possible targets; the spacecraft will simply have nothing else to look at. After Galileo's first orbit, typical apojooves will be $100\text{--}150 R_J$. The wider fields are to be preferred for halo studies, because they capture a larger piece of the whole; from shorter distances, the individual frames will show too little variation to be useful. The halo's $\sim 20,000$ km total vertical extent will fill the frame near $50 R_J$.

Considering the scarce data currently available, virtually any new images would put additional observational constraints on the system. Higher resolution frames, preferably with diminished smear, will help clarify the system's structure. Additional phase angle coverage, especially at multiple wavelengths, will further constrain the sizes and properties of the ring's constituent bodies. Views from a range of elevations will help to refine the

halo's vertical structure; this in turn will allow the halo contribution to the main ring to be removed, and the ring's photometry thereby improved. Temporal and longitudinal coverage will be needed to identify any asymmetries or variations with the magnetic field. Long exposures at low phase angles could help locate any additional satellites, and further constrain the orbits of the known ones. Long exposures at or beyond the bright ring ansa, particularly in forward-scatter, should have no trouble detecting the faint external ring and any structure in it. In addition, the spacecraft's Near-Infrared Mapping Spectrometer will constrain the surface compositions of the nearby satellites, and perhaps the ring as well.

However, a number of specific, diagnostic ring observations need specialized geometry, and therefore will require specific advanced planning. First, a very high-resolution mosaic across the ansa could reveal any very fine structure which might be present in the bright ring, as well as the best determinations of the system's boundaries. The ring should be viewed from the shortest possible range and highest possible elevation, and preferably in forward-scatter, where it is brightest. Since Galileo's proposed trajectory includes only one pass into the inner satellite region (on its insertion orbit), this is the ideal time to obtain an image set with the maximum possible resolution on the ring. That resolution will be better than 5 km/pixel.

Second, a better measurement of the ring's thickness would be

valuable. This is best accomplished by an ansa image as the spacecraft crosses the ring plane at close range. A brief exposure time, to minimize smear, is also desirable. Such a frame may also help to put a direct limit on the ring's optical depth; if the ring is thin enough, then it can become optically thick along an in-plane line of sight. This could be detected as a temporary diminution of the ring's intensity during the ring plane crossing. In effect, we would see the ring shadowing itself. Attempted occultations, by the Radio Science and Photopolarimeter-Radiometer experiments, might impose additional constraints.

Finer information in the halo's structure will be easy to acquire from shadow-boundary views, using the "slicing" technique demonstrated in §5.2. These, by their very nature, must be taken from within or near Jupiter's shadow. Since they are views of a diffuse, vertically-extended cloud, resolution is less critical; images from 50-100 R_J will be adequate for the procedure.

For theoretical models, it would be very useful to know the properties of the plasma and magnetic field near the ring. However, at best these numbers will have to be extrapolations from the Energetic Particle Detector measurements made farther out, since the spacecraft never reaches this close to the planet. Considerable new information about the local micrometeoroid flux will be provided by the Dust Detector, which may allow determinations of how many parent bodies are needed to supply the ring's micron-sized grains, and whether an additional source of impacting

particles, such as Io-derived dust, is necessary.

Finally, although the Galileo orbiter will never pass very close to the ring system, the atmospheric probe will. Its Lightning and Energetic Particles experiment will make direct plasma measurements of the inner magnetosphere, on its way to the Jovian cloudtops. In fact, depending on its entry latitude, the probe may pass directly through the outer reaches of the halo. This could yield useful information, but the possible hazard to the entry probe may be unacceptable.

9.4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This research has provided considerable new insight into the physical properties of Jupiter's ring system. Our results relate to all aspects of the system's structure and form, as well as to the properties of its member particles. In so doing, we have developed and demonstrated a number of interpretive techniques, applicable whenever signal, resolution and geometry in an image are less than ideal.

These techniques have applications to many Voyager images of Saturn's rings, particularly those taken during ring plane crossing and of the faint D, E, G and possibly F rings. It is likely that similar procedures will also be useful for interpreting the Voyager Uranus images of January 1986. Voyager's rapid motion almost normal to the ring plane will enhance smear in many frames, and the problem will be exacerbated by the long exposures needed for a

planet so distant from the sun. Even with Galileo's much improved imaging at Jupiter, our techniques for deconvolving the light from overlapping faint features, such as the ring and halo, will be applicable.

Although we have attempted to place all of our observations into a theoretical context, we have not attempted (as yet) to construct a single quantitative model for the Jovian ring system's dynamics. That may require more information about the system than is currently available; unfortunately, many more new results do not seem to be obtainable from the data now in hand. Nevertheless, we hope that our study has rekindled some interest in Jupiter's neglected but provocative ring system, and has also laid the foundation upon which a more complete understanding will one day be built.

APPENDIX A
A PRIMER ON PLANETARY IMAGE GEOMETRY

A.1 IMAGE CONTENT

Features within a Voyager image may be easily referenced to an Instrument Coordinate System (ICS), defined by a triad of unit vectors centered on the spacecraft. This frame is oriented such that the z-axis is directed along the camera's line of sight, while the x- and y-axes run parallel to the samples and lines, respectively, of the pixel grid.

However, this coordinate frame translates with the spacecraft position and rotates with the camera, so it is an inconvenient one for discussions of the physical locations of pictured bodies. For this purpose, the most convenient frame is often the Planet Mean Equator and Equinox (PMEE), an inertial frame centered on the central body, and oriented such that the z-axis points along its rotation axis, while the x-axis is directed toward the ascending node of its orbit on the equator. This is especially convenient for planetary rings, which tend to reside in the planet's equatorial plane defined by $z = 0$. For planetary surfaces, one could readily transform from this frame to a rotating one, in which surface features are fixed.

Transformation between these frames is usually performed via

a third frame, the standard Earth Mean Equator and Equinox (EMEE), defined analogously to the PMEE frame above. The C matrix is the transformation matrix from ICS to EMEE:

$$\tilde{X}_{EMEE} = \underset{\sim}{C} \tilde{X}_{ICS} \quad [A.1]$$

The T matrix is defined as the transformation from PMEE to EMEE:

$$\tilde{X}_{EMEE} = \underset{\sim}{T} \tilde{X}_{PMEE} \quad [A.2]$$

Since all coordinate frames are defined by a triad of orthogonal, right-handed unit vectors, these matrices are "unitary", i.e., their inverses equal their transposes. These matrices are cataloged in the Supplementary Experiment Data Record (SEDR) associated with each Voyager image, along with numerous other parameters describing the exposure and its geometry. A direct conversion matrix $\underset{\sim}{C}'$ from ICS to PMEE is readily constructed from the product of these matrices:

$$\underset{\sim}{C}' = \underset{\sim}{T}^{-1} \underset{\sim}{C} = \underset{\sim}{T}^{\dagger} \underset{\sim}{C} \quad [A.3]$$

For convenience, in the following discussion we will dispense with both the intermediate frame and the "prime" notation, so $\underset{\sim}{C}$ will be the transformation matrix directly from ICS to PMEE.

Let us consider a feature at a specific location \underline{p} in space which falls at (line, sample) coordinate (ℓ, s) in a Voyager image. Let \underline{v} be the spacecraft location and $\underline{l} = (\underline{p} - \underline{v})$ be a vector along the line of sight from Voyager to the target point.

We will also make frequent use of the unit line-of-sight vector \underline{l}_1 , which satisfies

$$\underline{l}_1 = \frac{\underline{p} - \underline{v}}{a} \quad [\text{A.4}]$$

or, by rearranging,

$$\underline{p} = \underline{v} + a\underline{l}_1, \quad [\text{A.5}]$$

where $a = |\underline{l}|$ is the distance to the point of interest. \underline{l}_1 may be readily expressed in the ICS:

$$\underline{l}_1^{\text{ICS}} = \frac{(p_x, p_y, 1)^{\dagger}}{(p_x^2 + p_y^2 + 1)^{1/2}}, \quad [\text{A.6}]$$

where

$$p_x = (s - \frac{n}{2}) \cdot \frac{\text{FOV}}{n}; \quad [\text{A.7a}]$$

$$p_y = (\ell - \frac{n}{2}) \cdot \frac{\text{FOV}}{n}. \quad [\text{A.7b}]$$

Here n is the number of pixels in a line and FOV is the angular span (in radians) of the field of view. Note that $p_x, p_y \ll 1$; since FOV is small, L_{1ICS} never deviates far from the z -axis. Equations [A.7] are only rigorously valid in a geometrically corrected image; distortion in uncorrected Voyager images makes the mapping from (λ, s) to (p_x, p_y) nonlinear.

Now it is a straightforward matter to calculate either the location on an image of any feature in the field or, conversely, the location in space of a feature on an image. In the former case, given \underline{p} , we calculate L_{1PMEE} from [A.4], convert to L_{1ICS} by C^{-1} , and then to (λ, s) by [A.6] and [A.7].

In the other direction, an additional constraint such as the distance a to the target point \underline{p} must be given, since an infinity of points lie along any line of sight. From (λ, s) we determine L_{1ICS} by [A.6] and [A.7], transform to L_{1PMEE} , and then calculate \underline{p} from [A.5]. For example, to calculate the location of a ring feature, we must solve for a such that the z -component of \underline{p} vanishes:

$$a = \frac{(P_z - V_z)}{L_{1z}} . \quad [A.8]$$

To calculate the location of a planetary surface feature such as a crater or cloud, we must solve for a such that \underline{p} is a planetary radius R_p distant from the origin:

$$R_p = |y + a_{z1}|, \quad [A.9]$$

a simple quadratic. The larger solution may be discarded, since it corresponds to a point out of sight on the far side of the planet. If necessary, planetary oblateness may be incorporated into [A.9], by rescaling all z-coordinates to make the planet effectively spherical.

A.2 POINTING CORRECTIONS

The above discussion would be all one needs to know about image geometry if one could rely upon the C matrix to be exactly correct at all times. Unfortunately, the Voyager cameras pointed imperfectly, so image features are often displaced slightly from their predicted locations.

A simple correction may be inserted by mapping each pixel coordinate (λ, s) to a new pair (λ', s') , via

$$\lambda' = \lambda \cdot \cos\theta + s \cdot \sin\theta + \Delta\lambda \quad [A.10a]$$

$$s' = -\lambda \cdot \sin\theta + s \cdot \cos\theta + \Delta s. \quad [A.10b]$$

This involves three parameters: a rotation through angle θ and a vector translation by $(\Delta\lambda, \Delta s)$. Since only three Euler angles define the nine elements of a unitary matrix, this is equivalent to replacing the C matrix entirely. However, we have found that leaving \underline{C} unchanged (provided it is reasonably accurate) and inserting these corrections separately is preferable. First, θ is

generally quite tiny and can often be left at zero, so we need only determine two correction parameters instead of three. Second, image smear is much easier to describe in the above framework.

Determination of the correction parameters must be based upon the locations of known features in an image. Positions of known satellites, craters, rings or (preferably) stars can be measured, and a least-squares fit on parameters $(\theta, \Delta\lambda, \Delta s)$ performed to minimize the RMS distance between predicted and measured image locations. This is the procedure we have used in every Jovian ring image.

A.3 IMAGE SMEAR

For the lengthy exposures of this study, smear becomes a significant hindrance to unambiguous image interpretations. It may be understood as a change in the line of sight unit vector \underline{l}_{ICS} corresponding a specific point \underline{p} during the course of an exposure. Let us first consider changes in the full line-of-sight vector \underline{l} :

$$\underline{l}_{ICS} = (\underline{p} - \underline{v})_{ICS} = \underline{c}^\dagger (\underline{p} - \underline{v})_{PMEE} . \quad [A.11]$$

Differentiating,

$$d\underline{l}_{ICS} = d\underline{c}^\dagger (\underline{p} - \underline{v})_{PMEE} - \underline{c}^\dagger d\underline{v}_{PMEE} , \quad [A.12]$$

where we have assumed that \underline{p} is fixed, and so $d\underline{p} = 0$. Finally, we return to the unit vector:

$$d\tilde{L}_{1ICS} = d\left(\frac{\tilde{L}_{1ICS}}{a}\right) \approx \frac{d\tilde{L}_{1ICS}}{a} - \frac{da}{a^2} \tilde{L}_{1ICS} . \quad [A.13]$$

The second term in [A.13] may be ignored, because we are only interested in the x and y components of $d\tilde{L}_{1ICS}$, and these are smaller in the second term than in the first by a factor of FOV. Substituting [A.12] into [A.13] yields, finally,

$$d\tilde{L}_{1ICS} = d\tilde{C}_{\approx}^{\dagger} \tilde{L}_{1PMEE} - \tilde{C}_{\approx}^{\dagger} \frac{d\tilde{V}_{PMEE}}{a} . \quad [A.14]$$

Note that errors in \tilde{C}_{\approx} of order FOV may be neglected here (since they are comparable to errors we have already excluded), so there is no need to correct the C matrix pointing errors in this expression.

The final relation [A.14] contains two terms, each of which has a simple physical meaning. The first contains the change in \tilde{C}_{\approx} , and therefore represents the change in camera pointing during the exposure. It is represented by the star trails which are often visible as streaks in the dark background of images. The second term contains the change in Voyager's position during the exposures; it corresponds to the changing perspective on a nearby target as the spacecraft moves. This term is inversely proportional to target distance a , and so vanishes entirely for stars. A third component might arise if $d\tilde{P}$ is non-vanishing; this would be the case if \tilde{P} is, for example, the location of a satellite in Keplerian motion.

It is now apparent that star trails only represent a part of the smear in spacecraft images; under many circumstances the spacecraft motion term is just as large. Indeed, this term is variable over a frame since, in an inclined ring view, target distance will vary from point to point. Nevertheless, we can calculate this term in [A.14] and, by combining [A.6] and [A.7], determine smear vectors $(\delta\lambda, \delta s)$. These may then be added vectorially to the visible star trails, which correspond to the first term. Star trails are actually ambiguous, since we do not know a priori in which direction the star moved to leave behind its signature. Of the two possibilities, one may generally be discarded as obviously inconsistent with image contents. Further possibilities, such as that the star traced its trail more than once during the exposure period, may be rejected as extremely unlikely.

As an illustration, Fig. A.1 shows FDS 20692.53, a NA image with a prominent star trail. Smear vectors for the ring plane are overplotted at uniformly-spaced points of origin. One set, corresponding to a downward-moving star, indicates that the far (upper) ring arm should smear perpendicular to itself by only ~ 2 pixels. The other star direction would smear this region by greater than the scale of visible ring structure, and may therefore be discarded.

The stellar smear component may now be described by pointing correction parameters $(\Delta\lambda, \Delta s)$, which vary with time t during the exposure; in functional form, $\Delta\lambda(t)$ and $\Delta s(t)$ are often linear. No

measurable change in θ during an exposure has ever been found. If we were instead to omit these terms and revise the C matrix, we would have slightly different C matrices at the beginning and end of an exposure. Unfortunately, interpolation between the two C matrices (to understand the image at intermediate times) is quite difficult, because a linear average of two unitary matrices is not unitary. Disastrous problems can arise inside a numerical code when a matrix assumed to be unitary is not. To avoid ever having to interpolate and then re-orthogonalize \underline{C} , we simply regard $\Delta\lambda$ and Δs as the time-variable quantities.

FIGURE A.1. We plot the predicted smear for points on the ring plane in FDS 20692.53, depending on the direction of motion in the visible star trail (next to arrow).
 a) For the star moving downward, smear runs nearly parallel to the far (upper) ring arm.
 b) For the star moving upward, the far ring arm would have smeared to nearly double its true width. This possibility may be rejected.

APPENDIX B

LIGHT SCATTERING BY PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTIONS

B.1 SINGLE-PARTICLE SCATTERING

Detailed discussions of the scattering of light by particles may be found in numerous other sources (van de Hulst, 1981; Hansen and Travis, 1974; see also Appendix of Cuzzi et al., 1984). Here we will summarize those results which are most applicable to our investigations of the Jovian ring system.

When incident light interacts with a particle, some of it is absorbed (to ultimately be re-radiated thermally), while the remainder is scattered off into new directions. The amount which is scattered may be described by a cross section C_{scat} , such that if F is the incident flux density, then $C_{\text{scat}}F$ is the scattered flux. This area may be related to the particle's physical cross section G (which equals πr^2 for a spherical grain), by the dimensionless scattering efficiency Q_{scat} :

$$Q_{\text{scat}} = \frac{C_{\text{scat}}}{G} . \quad [\text{B.1}]$$

The amount absorbed can be related, in an analogous manner, to an absorption cross section C_{abs} or an absorption efficiency Q_{abs} . The total light removed from the incident beam is called

the extinction, which represents the sum of that scattered and absorbed. It too may be related to an efficiency factor:

$$Q_{\text{ext}} = Q_{\text{scat}} + Q_{\text{abs}} \cdot \quad [\text{B.2}]$$

Under the circumstances we consider, these efficiencies are only weakly dependent on the shape of a particle (Pollack and Cuzzi, 1980).

The distribution of scattered light as a function of angular direction (θ, ϕ) is described by a phase function $P(\theta, \phi)$, which is normalized to 4π when integrated over all solid angles. For spherical grains (or for an average over randomly-oriented grains), P is simply a function of scattering angle θ , defined as the angle between the directions of the incident and scattered beams. Symmetry eliminates all dependence on the azimuthal angle. For astronomical usage, it is common to work with the phase angle α , equal to the supplement of θ .

These quantities are sufficient to describe the intensity of light scattered by a particle, provided the polarization states of the light may be ignored. Not surprisingly, the quantities are strong functions of particle size and composition. The former is described by the nondimensional size parameter $X = 2\pi r/\lambda$, while the latter is contained in the grain's complex refractive index m .

The asymptotic limit of very small particles ($X \ll 1$) shows the relatively simple Rayleigh-scattering behavior. The tiny grains become almost transparent to light, such that $Q_{\text{scat}} \propto X^4$.

What little light they do scatter is symmetric between forward- and back-scatter, and nearly isotropic:

$$P(\theta) = \frac{3}{4} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) . \quad [\text{B.3}]$$

As X increases, we reach a regime where particles are comparable to, or somewhat larger than the wavelength ($1 < X \lesssim 100$). In this domain particles tend to diffract most of their light into a narrow forward lobe, of angular spread $\theta \approx \pi/X$. Particles in this size range therefore tend to be very bright in forward-scatter relative to backscatter.

For still larger sizes we reach the geometric optics limit, where the wave nature of the light is no longer dominant. In this limit $Q_{\text{ext}} = 2$, in what has been called Babinet's Paradox (see van de Hulst, 1981, pp. 105-108). One might have expected that $Q_{\text{ext}} = 1$ for large bodies, since the extinguished light from a beam is simply that which intersects the surface. However, an equal amount of light is diffracted by the body, thereby doubling the extinction. This diffracted light falls into the forward lobe, which for large bodies becomes extremely narrow. It is often indistinguishable from the incident wave, unless we can measure its nonzero phase shift, as in, for example, the Voyager radio occultation of Saturn's rings. Neglecting the diffracted component, phase functions of large bodies tend to be primarily back-scattering. Rough bodies also tend to show a narrow "opposition

surge" in brightness within a few degrees of $\alpha = 0$, generally ascribed to mutual shadowing by tiny surface grains.

The Mie theory is an analytic method for calculating the scattering properties of a sphere, depending upon its size parameter X and refractive index m (cf. van de Hulst, 1981). It is based on an expansion of incident and scattered waves in terms of spherical Bessel functions, which are then solved for the appropriate boundary conditions on a spherical surface. The result is a series solution, which converges in $\sim |m|X$ terms. It quickly reduces to the Rayleigh-scattering case for small X , and approaches the geometric optics limit for large X . All of the calculated phase functions in this thesis are based upon the Mie theory, using a computer program developed by J.B. Pollack and J.N. Cuzzi at NASA's Ames Research Center.

B.2 SCATTERING BY A SIZE DISTRIBUTION

It is certainly unreasonable to assume that any ring is composed of particles of only a single size. A physically-plausible size distribution may have a dispersion which is small or large, but it is certainly not zero. As in Chapter 2, we describe a population of ring particles by a size distribution n , such that $n(r)dr$ is the number of particles per unit ring plane area with sizes from r to $r + dr$. We wish to relate this distribution to the quantity $\tau \tilde{\omega}_0 P$, where τ is the optical depth, $\tilde{\omega}_0$ is the single-scattering albedo, and P is the overall phase function of the size

distribution. The product $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ can be calculated easily from the I/F values found in an image, by [2.14].

Each of the quantities composing $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ may be expressed in terms of integrals over the size distribution:

$$\tau = \int \pi r^2 \cdot Q_{\text{ext}}(r) \cdot n(r) dr ; \quad [\text{B.4}]$$

$$\tilde{\omega}_0 = \frac{\int \pi r^2 \cdot Q_{\text{scat}}(r) \cdot n(r) dr}{\int \pi r^2 \cdot Q_{\text{ext}}(r) \cdot n(r) dr} ; \quad [\text{B.5}]$$

$$P(\theta) = \frac{\int \pi r^2 \cdot Q_{\text{scat}}(r) \cdot P(\theta, r) \cdot n(r) dr}{\int \pi r^2 \cdot Q_{\text{scat}}(r) \cdot n(r) dr} . \quad [\text{B.6}]$$

Here the dependence of Q_{ext} , Q_{scat} and P on particle radius is explicitly included, while their dependence on m is implicit. By comparison of [B.4-6], the product $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ simplifies to the numerator of [B.6]:

$$\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P(\theta) = \int \pi r^2 Q_{\text{scat}}(r) \cdot P(\theta, r) \cdot n(r) dr \quad [\text{B.7}]$$

Thus $\tau\tilde{\omega}_0P$ has a simple representation in terms of both measurements (see [2.14]) and theory ([B.7] above). We use this relation in all of our predictions of scattered light from particle size distributions.

B.3 PROPERTIES OF A POWER-LAW SIZE DISTRIBUTION

One particularly simple and tractable size distribution is a power law, in which $n(r) = Cr^{-p}$ (see [6.2]). Distributions of this sort appear in a broad range of astrophysical situations, and exhibit a number of simple properties. Many of the properties were discussed qualitatively in §6.4; here we derive them in a rigorous manner.

We can substitute [6.2] into the integrals of [B.4-6], and replace r by X throughout. This yields

$$\tau = C \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{2\pi}\right)^{3-p} \cdot \int \pi X^2 \cdot Q_{\text{ext}}(X) \cdot X^{-p} dX ; \quad [\text{B.8}]$$

$$\tilde{\omega}_0 = \frac{\int \pi X^2 \cdot Q_{\text{scat}}(X) \cdot X^{-p} dX}{\int \pi X^2 \cdot Q_{\text{ext}}(X) \cdot X^{-p} dX} ; \quad [\text{B.9}]$$

$$P(\theta) = \frac{\int \pi X^2 \cdot Q_{\text{scat}}(X) P(\theta, X) \cdot X^{-p} dX}{\int \pi X^2 \cdot Q_{\text{scat}}(X) \cdot X^{-p} dX} . \quad [\text{B.10}]$$

Note that every integrand here is now independent of wavelength λ . Possible wavelength dependence in the integration limits will be discussed below. These equations have rather startling consequences. First, they suggest that a power-law size distribution exhibits a phase function which is independent of wavelength. Also, τ (and hence $\tau \tilde{\omega}_0^p$) scales as a power of the wavelength:

$$\frac{\tau_1}{\tau_2} = \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2}\right)^{3-p} . \quad [\text{B.11}]$$

Thus, the ratio of intensities from a power law distribution at different wavelengths is a constant, and that constant relates to the power law index. For the special case of $p = 3$, even the intensity measured is independent of wavelength.

The above discussion does carry a few simplifications, however. Generally a power-law distribution must have lower and upper size limits (r_{\min} , r_{\max}). Outside the specified range, the index may change or another size distribution may take over. Cutoffs introduce limits of integration $X_{\min} = 2\pi r_{\min}/\lambda$ and $X_{\max} = 2\pi r_{\max}/\lambda$ in [B.4-7]; thus the integrals are no longer truly wavelength-invariant. In addition, any variation of refractive index with λ can insert some wavelength-dependence.

Luckily, for many purposes the precise upper and lower cutoff values are not important. Since tiny Rayleigh-scattering particles scatter so weakly, the lower limit X_{\min} , if less than ~ 1 , is rarely critical. The upper cutoff can play a role however, particularly for the flatter distributions (i.e., $p < 3$), but even then its importance depends on what is being measured. For example, the light contribution from larger bodies in forward-scatter drops off precipitously once their diffraction lobe becomes narrower than the smallest scattering angle observed. Under such circumstances, the scattering from a power-law distribution will show all of the special properties discussed above.

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